

Fatigue reduction in floating offshore wind turbines using tuned mass dampers

A modelling approach in the frequency domain

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Declaration

I hereby declare that except where specific reference is made to the work of others, the contents of this dissertation are original and have not been submitted in whole or in part for consideration for any other degree or qualification in this, or any other university. This dissertation is my own work and contains nothing which is the outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text and Acknowledgements. This dissertation contains less than 20 000 words excluding appendices, footnotes, tables and equations and has fewer than 150 figures.

Nicolas Fatras
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Abstract

This study focuses on the fatigue behaviour of a semi-submersible floating offshore wind turbine. Using Lagrange's equation of motion, a simplified model of the system is set up in the frequency domain, taking into account wind and ocean wave external forces. The frequency domain's faster computation times allow to test the model for a wider range of environmental conditions and subsequently optimise a passive control system over a larger range of parameters.

To operate in the frequency domain, linearisation methods are applied to some forces. If the ensuing results are not accurate enough, frequency transformations from time-domain outputs are taken from the literature to correctly represent highly non-linear forces. The model shows that although the response at natural frequencies of the platform is barely affected by ocean wave frequencies, the wave lengths of typical marine excitation forces cause in-phase loading of the semi-submersible's cylinders, which results in an undesirable peak response in the ocean wave frequency range.

Based on the dynamic model results, an analysis of the fatigue loads at the tower base is obtained from the differential movement between the floating platform and the tower. The frequencies contributing the most to fatigue are identified, taking into account the probability distribution of the frequency content of the external forces based on local weather data. Results show that most of the fatigue damage is caused by the peak identified in the ocean wave frequency range.

Finally, tuned mass dampers (TMD) are used for fatigue reduction in the identified critical frequency range. The TMDs' efficiency is measured by the Damage Equivalent Load (DEL) reduction at the tower base. A parametric study is done to evaluate the optimal characteristics of the TMDs, including mass, position, damping coefficient, stiffness and total number of dampers. Using a single TMD, a DEL reduction of 6.7% is achieved, which corresponds to a 23% increase in structural lifetime. Using multiple TMDs over a wider range of frequencies does not show sufficient improvements to be beneficial. This report concludes that passive control of floating wind turbines using TMDs is effective but that considerable fatigue behaviour improvement could also be achieved through careful redesign of the semi-submersible's geometric and structural properties.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 The current state of the wind industry in Europe

Wind power generation has developed over the past two decades in Europe from a nascent industry to a mature sector of the power industry with a generation capacity of 169GW in 2017 [25]. Wind power covered 11.6% of the EU’s electricity demand and represented 55% of the EU’s newly installed power capacity in 2017 [25]. Following this momentum, the offshore wind sector has also made considerable progress over the last few years as shown in Figure 1.1, motivated by several reasons. Firstly, the higher and more consistent average wind speeds out at sea allow to reach capacity factors (average output power over rated power) of 60% for offshore turbines while onshore turbines are typically around 25% [21]. Additionally, offshore turbines are considered less invasive, which is becoming more and more relevant as undeveloped onshore sites with high potential and low land competition are getting rarer.

Source: WindEurope

Fig. 1.1 Cumulative and annual offshore wind energy installation in Europe [56]

The majority of offshore wind farms installed so far have used foundations fixed to the seabed. As the industry is chasing higher wind speeds, sea depths are also increasing which requires more capital intensive installations. Most installations remain under 50m water depth for economic viability reasons. This is made clear when analysing the installed and planned projects shown in Figure 1.2.

Fig. 1.2 Sea depth and distance from shore of fixed offshore projects in Europe [56]

However a large amount of wind resources lies out at seas with more than 60m depth, as shown in Figure 1.3, and remains largely unexploited as of today. Floating wind turbine foundations, which consist of a floating platform anchored to the seabed, were shown to be more economically competitive from these depths onward [23]. Floating wind turbines are therefore considered as the next essential step in the development of the offshore wind industry.

Fig. 1.3 Weather characteristics of Northwestern European seas (maps drawn using [54])

Additionally, Figure 1.3 shows that areas with higher winds also imply higher wave forces, to which floating platforms are particularly sensitive. The platforms on which the turbines rest must be designed to minimise the impact of these wave forces on the turbine's motion, as large motions affect the aerodynamics (and therefore the power output) of the turbine and increase the structural loading on the turbine's components [42].

1.2 State of the art in FOWTs

A wide range of platform prototypes have been suggested for floating offshore wind turbines (FOWT), which shows the technology still lacks industrial standards. Figure 1.4 shows the most common platform types.

Fig. 1.4 Floating platform types [31]

Each platform has its own stabilising mechanism, with benefits and disadvantages. These are summarised in Table 1.1.

Table 1.1 Comparison of main floating platform types (based on information provided in [38])

Platform type	Stabilising mechanism	Advantages	Disadvantages
Spar	Ballast force from low centre of gravity	Low wave sensitivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deep draft (120m for OC3-Hywind spar buoy) • Large size implies difficult construction and installation
TLP	Mooring cables	High natural periods outside of wind and wave excitation frequencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Installation made difficult by anchorage process • Higher dependence on local geological conditions
Barge	Buoyancy (large waterplane second moment of area)	Easy construction and installation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Higher wave sensitivity • Low natural frequencies close to wind excitation frequencies

The semi-submersible is a hybrid of these different concepts. It typically consists of three offset cylinders which provide a buoyancy restoring force but which are also immersed enough to provide a ballast force. The mooring lines play a stabilising role as well. The semi-submersible's shallow draft and good stability in both operational and transit conditions give it a competitive edge over the other platforms [59]. This study therefore focuses on floating wind turbines with a semi-submersible platform.

1.3 The importance of designing for the long term

A few demonstration projects such as Fukushima FORWARD completed in 2013 have demonstrated the full-scale feasibility of semi-submersible FOWTs [35]. To successfully penetrate the energy market, the current focus of FOWT designers is to reduce the energy production cost from floating turbines [13]. As floating turbines have relatively high upfront capital costs, this can be achieved by extending their operation lifetime. However the long-term resistance of floating wind turbines to fatigue from variable wind and wave loads remains uncertain and could be a major hurdle to extending the structure's lifetime. According to [38], tower-base bending moment fatigue loads are 2.5 higher for spar platforms than for onshore turbines, and this sea-to-land ratio goes up to 7 for barge platforms. In fact [30] states that a majority of reported offshore structural failures are due to fatigue. This study will therefore focus on the fatigue resistance of semi-submersible FOWTs and on structural solutions to maximise fatigue load reductions.

Chapter 2

Background and literature review

2.1 Structural control options

To reduce fatigue loads on a structure, different options exist which aim to reduce the amplitude and frequency of vibrations in the structure. Passive control does not require any external input and relies on the physical properties of the controller to change the structure's response. Active control implies external power input with a feedback system to adapt the controller to external forces.

2.1.1 Passive control

Passive control modifies the structural properties of the primary system to change its response to external excitations. Tuned mass dampers (TMD) are a common form of passive controllers [64] and consist of a mass attached to the main structure with a spring and damper. If tuned appropriately, the spring will cause a restoring force on the structure as the TMD moves opposite to the structure. The damper dissipates the acquired energy in the form of heat. Another option is the tuned liquid column damper (TLCD) which operates with water oscillating within a U-tube to create a restoring force with an orifice in the middle to create a damping force in the flow. A schematic of each system is shown in Figure 2.1.

2.1.2 Active control

Active structural control methods use actuators to apply balancing forces on the structure and adapt the structural properties to incoming external forces. This allows them to be more effective as they cover a broader range of frequencies and can apply higher forces to the structure. An example is the active mass damper (AMD), where the counteracting forces on the mass added to the structure come from the actuator instead of the spring and damper [64]. In [43] the use of an AMD on a floating barge wind turbine reduced fatigue loads by 30% while the use of a passive TMD only achieved 10% fatigue load reduction. Another active control method is pitch control of individual

(c) Schematic of TLCD [64]

Fig. 2.1 Schematics of common passive structural control mechanisms

blades when they operate in turbulent conditions or above rated speed. This allows to reduce the thrust on the turbine and therefore reduces the destabilising moment on the turbine. However, this can also lead to greater power variability and blade root fatigue [32].

In general, the operation of active control systems requires power input and they often consist of electromechanical devices with have a higher likelihood of failure, which can be costly in terms of maintenance if the wind turbines are far out at sea. A last drawback is the feedback frequency of active control systems, which could lead to instabilities if not adjusted to the structure properly.

While active control methods have higher potential control benefits, they also involve higher risks. As floating wind turbines still are very much in the prototype stage, the more reliable passive control method is preferred in this study. The challenge is to achieve a flexible passive control

system which can operate under a variety of loading conditions. TMDs oscillating along a horizontal axis are chosen as the passive control of choice due to the possibility of easily installing TMDs with different properties throughout the structure.

2.2 Tuned mass dampers theory

2.2.1 Basic principle

As mentioned above, the tuned mass damper is a passive vibration control system which consists of a mass connected to the main structure with a certain stiffness and damping value. It can therefore be considered as a SDOF with base excitation. Transmissibility curves are usually used to represent the response of SDOFs as a function of vibration frequency. Such curves represent the ratio of response amplitude to excitation amplitude. Figure 2.2 gives transmissibility curves examples for different damping values.

Fig. 2.2 Transmissibility curve of base excited SDOF [17]

The stiffness and the mass of the TMD determine its natural frequency and therefore the location of the peak response. The damping value determines the amplitude of the peak. Below the natural frequency, the transmissibility ratio is equal to 1 which means the TMD follows the motion of the primary structure. At the TMD's natural frequency, the large motions of the TMD create the desired restoring force on the primary structure through the TMD's stiffness and damping. At vibration

frequencies much higher than the natural frequency, the TMD tends to stay in place compared to the primary structure which means that its stiffness and damping contribute as a restoring force but not to the same extent as at peak response.

In general, TMDs reduce vibrations through two mechanisms. First, by adding a TMD to a structure, another degree of freedom is added to the system, which creates a second peak in the response of the primary structure. If the natural frequency of the TMD is tuned appropriately, it can shift the natural frequency of the primary system outside of the main excitation frequency and therefore reduce the overall motion of the system. This is exemplified by the curve $\xi_d = 0.0$ in Figure 2.3

Fig. 2.3 Impact of TMD on SDOF primary structure [18]

If the main excitation frequency Ω happens to occur at the natural frequency ω of the primary system, the response would be very large. Adding a TMD allows to avoid a large response in this region, at the cost of higher response either side of the initial ω . The optimal location of these two peaks depends on the frequency content of the input signal.

TMDs also reduce vibration through their own damping value. The damper installed in TMDs is typically a viscoelastic material which dissipates energy in the form of heat [51]. From Figure 2.3, it is clear that adding damping allows to reduce the peak values either side of ω . However, if damping is too high the TMD will not be able to have a relative motion and will simply follow the primary structure. At this point it reverts back to an SDOF system with additional damping, which corresponds to the curve with $\xi_d = 0.1$ in Figure 2.3 and the curve with $Q = 1$ in Figure 2.2, which shows a transmissibility near 1 at resonant frequency.

2.2.2 Advantage of using MTMDs

In reality, offshore structures have multiple degrees of freedom and undergo a whole range of vibration frequencies due to varying environmental conditions. A TMD tuned for one load case could become detrimental for another. Multiple tuned mass dampers allow to take into account a much broader range of excitation frequencies. The effect of increasing the TMD number is shown in Figure 2.4.

Fig. 2.4 Harmonic response of the displacement of the primary system to base excitation with various numbers of dampers n for $\mu = 5\%$ and $\eta_s = 0$: $n=0$ (dot), $n=1$ (dash-dot), $n=2$ (dash), $n=5$ (thick-solid), $n=100$ (solid) [73]

The optimisation problem consists in choosing the appropriate number of TMDs and the right mass, stiffness, damping and position within the structure for each TMD. This quickly becomes very computationally expensive if many loading conditions are simulated. According to [73], for the optimisation of TMD properties on a SDOF primary system, the optimal tuning frequencies should not be equally spaced, and the damping coefficient should not be the same for every TMD. On the other hand the mass distribution amongst TMDs doesn't have much influence so a uniform mass distribution is acceptable [73]. In this report the effect of each parameter will be assessed individually for a first screening of optimal conditions before a general optimal configuration is found.

2.3 Literature review on TMD optimisation

2.3.1 Optimisation methods

The use of TMDs for vibration control of tall slender structures has received attention for several decades, with particular focus on stochastic wind and earthquake loads on tall buildings. While the tuned mass damper's mechanism is relatively straightforward, selecting the appropriate parameters suited for different operation conditions can become challenging, especially when multiple TMDs are installed. Each TMD will only be active around a particular frequency and can become detrimental at other vibration frequencies. Different optimisation methods have been used in the literature.

The exhaustive method selects a number of parameters to optimise and sets a range for each parameter. All the different combinations are then simulated and the best performing value is the optimal solution. For example, [48] focuses on optimising the mass, damping ratio and stiffness of a single TMD to minimise the relative displacement of an undefined SDOF. Preliminary results of the study found that increasing the TMD mass monotonically increases the performance of the system. An upper bound for the range must therefore be fixed based on economic and installation feasibility factors. This can however become quite computationally expensive if multiple TMDs are to be installed.

Den Hartog in [19] helps narrowing down the options by giving the optimal natural frequency $\omega_{TMD_{opt}}$ and damping ratio ξ_{opt} of a single TMD on a SDOF.

$$\omega_{TMD_{opt}} = \frac{1}{1 + \mu} * \omega_{structure} \quad (2.1)$$

$$\xi_{TMD_{opt}} = \sqrt{\frac{3\mu}{8(1 + \mu)}} \quad (2.2)$$

where $\mu = \frac{m_{TMD}}{mass_{structure}}$ is the mass ratio of the TMD. According to [63], the mass ratio in most vibration control applications is below 5%.

For a MDOF structure, there is no analytical solution for optimal tuning and numerical methods must be used [64]. The most critical peak frequencies have to be identified so that the TMDs can be matched to those frequencies, using Den Hartog's optimal values as a guideline rather than a fixed result. For MTMDs, $\omega_{TMD_{opt}}$ can be taken as the mean frequency value around which the different TMDs' natural frequencies are uniformly spread.

[72] uses MTMDs to control the vibrations of a fixed monopile offshore wind turbine subjected to wind, wave and earthquake loads. To simplify the problem, Zuo et al. set the mass and the damping value to be the same for each TMD and set their natural frequencies to be uniformly distributed about a target mean.

2.3.2 Modelling in the frequency domain

Irrespective of the chosen optimisation method, simulations of FOWT dynamics with added TMDs have to be run for multiple TMD configurations under many different environmental conditions. On a standard personal computer's processor, the simulation time for FOWT models with full structural, hydrodynamic and aerodynamic coupling will take around 10min using an established time-domain solver such as FAST-SC for a simulated time of 10 to 30 minutes [64]. The simulation to CPU time ratio is effectively 1. This is because numerical methods must solve the equation of motion ODE at each time step while maintaining acceptable accuracy and stability. This clearly limits the range of parameters to be tested.

Taking the Fourier transform of the equation of motion, the dynamics of the structure can be solved in the frequency domain (see section 3.1.2). In this case, the motions of the system are solved through simple linear algebra. The minimum frequency governs the time interval covered while the maximum frequency determines the timestep resolution. The computing efficiency of the frequency domain is made clear in [47], which models a spar floating wind turbine in the frequency domain. According to [47], the simulation of the entire coupled FOWT system in the frequency domain is 1200 times faster than the equivalent time-domain model using the commercial software "Bladed", assuming equivalent computing power.

However the frequency domain has a major drawback. As it is based on linear algebra, it requires the linearisation of non-linear forces. This is mainly a problem for hydrodynamic drag forces and aerodynamic forces in general which depend on velocity squared. Linearisation methods exist for hydrodynamic drag forces ([10]) and aerodynamic forces([60]), but are only valid for certain operation conditions and can lead to accuracy loss.

For this reason, frequency domain models have mainly been developed in offshore engineering to solve hydrodynamic problems while time domain models have been developed for wind turbine design. Floating wind turbines are influenced by interacting hydrodynamic and aerodynamic forces and therefore the effect of wave and wind loads cannot be analysed separately. For this reason most developed softwares such as FAST or Bladed run their simulations in the time domain.

2.3.3 TMDs in offshore wind turbines

Most of the research done on TMDs in offshore wind turbine relies at least partially on time-domain softwares to validate their models and then to test their optimised TMD configuration against realistic loading conditions. This implies that only a few load cases can be applied within a reasonable simulation time.

[45], [63] and [64] all follow a similar procedure to optimise TMD parameters of FOWTs:

1. Set up a simplified model of a certain FOWT prototype in the time domain, focusing only on the DOF which affect the objective function the most. This allows for faster simulation times in the optimisation process.
2. Calibrate and validate the model using a fully coupled time-domain software like FAST.
3. Optimise the TMD parameters in the simplified model by minimising the structure's response to an initial displacement without external forces.
4. Test the optimised TMD configuration in fully coupled FAST software under a few pre-determined weather conditions.

This implies that the optimisation process is done without consideration of weather conditions and the benefits of the optimised solution are only tested against a few weather conditions which are usually extreme. Nonetheless, these studies mention a successful reduction in fatigue loads: [64] achieves 4.6% fatigue load reduction in a spar platform at 10m/s winds, while [45] reaches 7.78% fatigue load reduction in a semi-submersible at 10m/s winds but this value drops to 0.18% reduction at 18m/s winds. Clearly the efficiency of the TMD is weather dependent but the optimisation process in these papers neglects this. Therefore their approach is more relevant to Ultimate Limit State (ULS) design, where the design focuses on reducing the FOWT's highest response peaks. However, if fatigue life is considered (Serviceability Limit State (SLS)), the entire range of environmental conditions over the turbine's lifetime must be taken into account and must consider not only highest response peaks but also those causing most damage through repeated cycles. Fatigue analysis therefore takes wave and wind frequencies into consideration in the TMD design.

A few papers covered by the author on the modelling of offshore wind turbines dynamics and their vibration reduction are summarised in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1 Literature review summary

	Time domain	Frequency domain
Fixed turbine	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [24]: Fatigue design for monopile with STMD • [72]: ULS design for monopile with MTMDs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [40]: ULS design for monopile, no TMD • [67]: ULS design for monopile, no TMD
Floating turbine	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [64]: ULS design for spar, barge and TLP using STMD • [32]: ULS design for barge using STMD • [63]: ULS design for spar using STMD • [14]: ULS design for TLP using MTMD • [45]: ULS design for semi submersible using STMD • [20]: ULS design for spar using MTMD 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [5]: ULS design for TLP, no TMD • [41]: Fatigue design for semi submersible, no TMD

From this table, it appears that the literature extensively covers the analysis in the time domain of floating wind turbine dynamics with single tuned mass dampers for ULS design. In general, there is a clear lack of work in assessing the impact of TMDs on wind turbines using the frequency domain. Most analyses only focus on a few extreme load cases instead of fatigue loads throughout the structure's lifetime. This can be correlated to the fact that fatigue load analysis is very computationally expensive in the time domain. Finally, single TMDs are preferred over MTMDs, again probably because of computational costs.

It is also interesting to note that semi-submersibles are not amongst the most commonly modeled platform prototypes despite representing, as of 2017, the largest amount of installed full-scale FOWT prototypes [45]. This leaves another gap in conclusions drawn on the impact of TMDs on floating wind turbines. As each platform prototype has its own balancing mechanism, optimised

parameters for one could be detrimental for another.

A first fundamental difference between fixed turbines and floating turbines is the location of their natural frequencies. Monopiles are typically designed in the soft-stiff regime so that their fundamental frequencies are above the wave and rotor frequencies [9]. Floating foundations on the other hand are designed in the soft-soft regime, so that their fundamental frequencies are much lower than the wave frequencies. The impact on TMD parameters is important:

[24] amongst others recommends installing the TMD in the nacelle for fixed turbines, as this is where the largest motion amplitudes occur and the tower has similar vibration frequencies to the monopile. On the other hand, papers covering floating turbines diverge depending on the platform. [32] positions the TMD in the nacelle for a barge platform while for the spar foundation [64] recommends placing the TMD in the platform, which operates at much lower frequencies than the tower-nacelle assembly. The positioning of the TMDs within the structure is hence an important factor to take into account.

2.4 Aims and objectives

From the literature review given in the previous section, it appears that several points still need to be covered in the dynamic analysis of floating wind turbines to guarantee their efficient operation at sea. The aim of this thesis is to improve the fatigue lifetime of semi-submersible floating wind turbines using multiple tuned mass dampers. The analysis will consist of the following steps:

- Derivation and set up of a simplified FOWT model in the frequency domain including external wind and wave forces. Simplifications will be made according to a compromise between computation speed and accuracy of results with regards to fatigue damage.
- Calculation of the fatigue damage on the FOWT taking into account the probabilistic distribution of weather conditions throughout its lifetime, at various locations in Northern European seas
- Evaluation of the impact of various TMD parameters (mass, stiffness, damping, position, frequency range) on the semi-submersible FOWT's behaviour. An overall optimisation with multiple TMDs will finally be done to evaluate the maximum potential fatigue lifetime improvement on a semi-submersible FOWT.

Chapter 3

Setting up the model

In order to assess fatigue loads on the structure, the dynamic behaviour of the FOWT under environmental loads first has to be modelled. Compromises are made in the modelling choices to balance accuracy of results with computation speed.

3.1 Model simplifications

The floating wind turbine system chosen for this study is the OC4 semi-submersible platform used in the DeepCwind project combined with the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) 5-MW baseline wind turbine. The OC4 platform consists of three offset cylinders connected with a bracing system and a smaller central cylinder supporting the turbine tower. The DeepCwind project allows for consistent and standardised comparisons of experimental and modelling data on floating wind turbines. Results available in the literature are used to calibrate and eventually validate the model set up in this research.

The analysis focuses on the fore-aft motion of the wind turbine as this is the direction in which most of the wind loading occurs, assuming the turbine has a built-in yaw mechanism. The model can therefore be analysed in the X-Z plane as two connected rigid bodies: the platform with two degrees of freedom (DOF) in surge and pitch and the tower with one DOF in pitch, as shown in Figure 3.1. The connection between the two bodies is modelled using a spring-dashpot system with values taken from Li et al. [45]. Li et al. model the same platform-turbine combination with the same base connection simplification, which they calibrate for structural base stiffness and damping values using outputs from time domain FAST simulations [45].

The simplified geometry and equilibrium state at rest are shown in Figure 3.1. In this planar view, the third offset cylinder is hidden behind the cylinder to the right of reference point P.

Fig. 3.1 Simplified model planar geometry

Note that heave motion has been neglected. This reduced DOF analysis is allowed due to the symmetry of the semi-submersible platforms which decouples the hydrodynamic forces on the structure [58], as will be shown later on. Three general variables therefore describe the platform and tower/nacelle/rotor motion: x_1 for DOF1, θ_1 for DOF2 and θ_2 for DOF3. The rigid body motions are all with respect to point P, which lies on the still water level (SWL) plane at the geometrical centre of the platform in the X-Y plane.

The analysis will focus on unidirectional aligned wind and wave inputs, which was shown to induce the biggest fatigue damage per amount of time [6]. This simplification can be considered a conservative and therefore safe assumption, as in reality wind and wave loads will sometimes be misaligned, reducing the loading component in the fore-aft plane.

To these three basic DOFs, a number n of TMDs restricted to uniaxial motion will be added. The equation of motion will therefore involve a $N = 3 + n$ MDOF system.

A virtual displacement $\delta\theta_1$ at DOF 2 would cause a displacement $\mathbf{d}r_2 = H_c * \delta\theta_1$ in the horizontal direction at the point of application of F_{wind} , so that the resulting work on the structure is $\delta W = F_{wind} * H_c * \delta\theta_1$. Adding the contribution of each DOF, the total virtual work from the wind force is:

$$\delta W = F_{wind}\delta x_1 + F_{wind}H_c\delta\theta_1 + F_{wind}R_{hub}\delta\theta_2$$

$$\delta W = F_{wind} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ H_c \\ R_{hub} \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \delta x_1 \\ \delta\theta_1 \\ \delta\theta_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

From equation 3.2 we can conclude:

$$Q_{wind} = F_{wind} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ H_c \\ R_{hub} \end{pmatrix}$$

This approach has to be repeated for every non-conservative force acting on the structure. As explained later on, these non-conservative forces consist of the damping terms in the equation of motion and the external excitations arising from wind and wave forces.

For a mechanical system, Lagrange's equation of motion can be simplified to equation 3.3 :

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial T(t)}{\partial \dot{q}_j} \right) + \frac{\partial V(t)}{\partial q_j} = Q_j(t) \quad (3.3)$$

The kinetic energy T takes into account the inertial forces on the structure and consists of the rotational and translational energy of the different bodies constituting the system. The potential energy V in this case consists of gravity and stiffness forces. Solving equation 3.3 for each general coordinate j , the standard equation of motion for a MDOF body is obtained in matrix notation:

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{x}}(t) + \mathbf{K}\mathbf{x}(t) = \mathbf{Q}(t) \quad (3.4)$$

The damping forces can be extracted from \mathbf{Q} and moved to the left hand side of the equation:

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{x}}(t) + \mathbf{C}\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) + \mathbf{K}\mathbf{x}(t) = \mathbf{Q}(t) \quad (3.5)$$

The various factors influencing the stiffness, damping and external excitation forces will be determined in sections 3.2 and 3.3 as a function of the structural, hydrodynamic and aerodynamic properties of the FOWT. The variables which constitute equation 3.3 will then be derived in more detail in section 3.4 while their resulting matrices are derived in Appendix A.

3.1.2 EOM in frequency domain

The force and the response functions can be considered to be composed of a superposition of signals of different amplitudes and frequencies. The Fourier transform of equation 3.5 yields the equation of motion in the frequency domain.

$$(-\omega^2 M + i\omega C + K)x(\omega) = Q(\omega) \quad (3.6)$$

which can be expressed as

$$x(\omega) = H(\omega) * Q(\omega) \quad (3.7)$$

where

$$H(\omega) = [-\omega^2 M + i\omega C + K]^{-1} \quad (3.8)$$

The response of the floating structure depends on its intrinsic structural, aerodynamic and hydrodynamic properties, represented by the transfer function $H(\omega)$, and the frequency content of the external forcing functions $Q(\omega)$. Wind and wave forces are obtained from a power spectral density of wave amplitudes and wind velocities, as will be shown in section 3.2. The equation of motion therefore has to be expressed using power spectral densities for the force and response functions.

The power spectral density (PSD) S_{xx} gives an indication of the frequency content of a signal x and is the Fourier transform of the autocorrelation function R_{xx} .

$$S_{xx}(\omega) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{\infty} R_{xx}(\tau) e^{-i\omega\tau} d\tau$$

with R_{xx} defined as :

$$R_{xx}(\tau) = E[x(t)x(t + \tau)]$$

Informally the autocorrelation function R_{xx} represents the amount of memory in a signal, that is to say the similarity of observations depending on the time lag between them [44].

Conveniently the integral of the power density spectrum over the whole frequency range corresponds to the mean squared value of the variable.

$$\sigma_x^2 = \int_0^{\infty} S_{xx}(\omega) d\omega \quad (3.9)$$

Note that wave and wind spectra are considered single-sided with only positive frequencies.

If a system can be considered linear, a straightforward input-output relation is obtained between the force spectrum S_{ff} and the response spectrum S_{xx} , which is derived in [44]:

$$S_{xx}(\omega) = |H(\omega)|^2 S_{ff}(\omega) \quad (3.10)$$

A relationship between the force spectrum and the input wave amplitude / wind velocity density spectrum $S_{\eta\eta}(\omega)$ can also be derived:

$$S_{ff}(\omega) = |q(\omega)|^2 S_{\eta\eta}(\omega) \quad (3.11)$$

where $q(\omega)$ is the external forcing function per unit wave height/wind speed amplitude.

The final form of the equation of motion used in the model to simulate the behaviour of the system subjected to random external forces is then written as:

$$S_{xx}(\omega) = |H(\omega) * q(\omega)|^2 S_{\eta\eta}(\omega) \quad (3.12)$$

3.2 Hydrodynamics

The pitch restoring mechanism of a semi-submersible platform is a combination of inertial forces (ballast) and waterplane moment of area (hydrostatic buoyancy) [38]. This makes the semi-submersible quite sensitive to its interaction with surrounding ocean conditions. The hydrodynamic stiffness, damping and excitation forces resulting from this interaction are therefore covered in the following section.

3.2.1 Wave spectra

Waves are generated from interaction of the wind with the sea surface. After the wind has interacted with the sea over a certain distance, the sea state is considered fully developed and can be treated as independent of local wind conditions [26]. In this case, the frequency spectra used for wind and wave forcing in the model could be completely uncorrelated.

One of the most common spectra used to describe the energy content (and therefore the wave amplitude distribution) of fully developed sea states is the Pierson-Moskowitz (PM) distribution, which only depends on the wave-generating wind velocity. In reality, sea states never reach a fully developed state. The JONSWAP spectrum was obtained from measurements taken in the North Sea and is a modification of the Pierson-Moskowitz spectrum to take into account the fetch distance (distance over which the generating wind acts over). However, measuring the fetch distance and the wind speeds over this distance is not straightforward when only local weather data is available for a specific site. Therefore the PM and JONSWAP spectra have been adapted to be expressed as a

function of the significant wave height H_s and the spectral peak period T_p measured at a point [52]. H_s is the mean height (trough to crest) of the highest ones-third waves over a given time while T_p is the period corresponding to the peak frequency of the wave energy spectrum [52].

The expression for the PM spectrum is therefore:

$$S_{PM}(\omega) = \frac{5}{16} H_s^2 \omega_p^4 \omega^{-5} \exp\left(-\frac{5}{4} \left(\frac{\omega}{\omega_p}\right)^{-4}\right) \quad (3.13)$$

where $\omega_p = \frac{2\pi}{T_p}$.

The non-fully developed sea state is taken into consideration by the JONSWAP spectrum as follows:

$$S_J(\omega) = A_\gamma S_{PM}(\omega) \gamma^{\exp\left(-0.5 \left(\frac{\omega - \omega_p}{\sigma \omega_p}\right)^2\right)} \quad (3.14)$$

where

$\gamma = 3.3$ is the non-dimensional peak shape parameter

$A_\gamma = (1 - 0.287 * \ln(\gamma))$ is a normalising factor

σ is the spectral width-parameter:

$\sigma = 0.07$ for $\omega \leq \omega_p$

$\sigma = 0.09$ for $\omega > \omega_p$

The difference between the two spectra is shown in Figure 3.3

Fig. 3.3 Comparison of PM and JONSWAP ocean waves PSD

The JONSWAP spectrum clearly results in a peakier response, which implies that excitations will be more concentrated at a specific frequency. The influence of H_s and T_p on the magnitude and frequency content of the JONSWAP spectrum is shown in figure 3.4. The peak frequency is marked as a reference point.

(a) Influence of significant wave height on JONSWAP spectrum

(b) Influence of peak spectral period on JONSWAP spectrum

Fig. 3.4 Influence of wave parameters on JONSWAP wave spectrum

The significant wave height influences the magnitude of the spectral peak while the peak period influences both the magnitude and the frequency of the wave range with the highest energy.

Each of these spectra with a specific combination of H_s and T_p will occur with a certain probability throughout the lifetime of the wind turbine. A study by [26] shows that for different locations around the British Isles, this probability distribution varies from site to site. Figure 3.5 shows how the probability distribution of T_p varies for different locations in northern Europe.

Fig. 3.5 Probability distribution of peak period T_p at different sites [26]

The x-axis on this figure corresponds to the inverse of the peak frequencies underlined in figure 3.4.

The range of wave conditions a FOWT can be subjected to over the course of its lifetime explains the importance of designing and testing the model for many different loading conditions. Additionally, each site will have to have its own set of simulations depending on local weather data. Being able to run each simulation relatively quickly in the frequency domain allows to cover a wide range of weather conditions without excessive computation time.

3.2.2 Ocean wave theory

Once a certain wave profile is obtained from the wave spectrum, wave-structure interactions can be calculated. Hydrodynamic loads on offshore structures usually include incident wave forces, radiation forces from the structure’s motion, and viscous forces [58]. The importance of each of

these forces will depend on the relative size of the structure with respect to the wave conditions. If the structure is relatively large compared to the wavelength and amplitude of the incoming waves, potential-flow theory can be used assuming non-separated flows, whereas smaller structures will tend to cause flow separation, in which case the empirical Morison's equation can be used [58].

Potential theory

The potential-flow theory is based on solving the incompressible, irrotational and inviscid version of the Navier-Stokes equation [8]. In 2D, this results in Laplace's differential equation:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial z^2} = 0 \quad (3.15)$$

where ϕ is the velocity potential. Boundary conditions at the sea bed assume a rigid impermeable surface while dynamic and kinematic boundary conditions at the surface are obtained by imposing a wave profile at equilibrium with atmospheric pressure.

The surface boundary condition can be linearised if the wave height is relatively small compared to the water depth and the wave length [8], which is a reasonable assumption for this study. This implies that wave effects at different frequencies can be analysed separately and then superimposed. A progressive harmonic wave profile is then represented as follows:

$$\eta = a \cos(kx - \omega t) = \Re(ae^{ikx}e^{-i\omega t}) \quad (3.16)$$

where a is the wave amplitude, k is the wave number ($k = \frac{2\pi}{L}$ where L is the wave length) and ω is the wave angular frequency ($\omega = \frac{2\pi}{T}$ where T is the wave period).

This wave profile is inserted into the free-surface boundary conditions. The linear approximation then allows to solve Laplace's equation together with the free-surface equation using the perturbation method up to a first order approximation (for a full derivation refer to [8]). The resulting velocity potential for a linear approximation is derived to be [8]:

$$\phi = \Re\left(-i \frac{ag}{\omega} \frac{\cosh(k(d-z))}{\cosh(kd)} e^{i(kx-\omega t)}\right) \quad (3.17)$$

For deep water conditions, which can be expected for FWOT installations, the term $\frac{\cosh(k(d-z))}{\cosh(kd)}$ can be simplified to e^{-kz} . The resulting velocity potential and the wave parameters derived from it which will be useful for the rest of this study are summarised in Table 3.1, using the results from [8].

Table 3.1 Wave parameters in deep water from linear wave theory (equations from [8])

Parameter	Description	Value
ϕ	Velocity potential in deep water	$\Re(-i\frac{ag}{\omega}e^{-kz}e^{i(kx-\omega t)})$
u	Horizontal wave velocity $u = \frac{d\phi}{dx}$	$\Re(\frac{agk}{\omega}e^{-kz}e^{i(kx-\omega t)})$
p_d	Wave dynamic pressure (ignoring velocity squared terms)	$\Re(-\rho age^{-kz}e^{i(kx-\omega t)})$
k	Dispersion relation in deep water	$k = \frac{\omega^2}{g}$

So far these wave properties have been derived by ignoring the boundary condition imposed by the semi-submersible itself in the water. This additional boundary condition is also moving in response to the external excitations. The modelling of the body's impermeable surface requires the use of source functions over the body surface, which then allow to solve for the potential function using integral equations [71]. As this is not the main focus of this study, hydrodynamic loadings per unit wave amplitude for the OC4 semi submersible will be obtained from WAMIT. WAMIT is a software using first order potential theory to solve hydrodynamic loads on structures using the panel method (a numerical method for integral equation solving) [69].

Morison's equation

If the body is small relative to the incoming wavelengths, flow separation becomes an important phenomenon and viscous drag must be taken into account. In this case Morison's equation can be used, which takes into account incident wave excitation, radiation added mass and viscous drag. Assuming an incoming wave of velocity u , the forces on a structure are as follows:

$$F = \frac{1}{2}C_d\rho D(u - \dot{q})|u - \dot{q}| + (1 + C_a)\rho \frac{\pi D^2}{4}\ddot{u} - C_a\rho \frac{\pi D^2}{4}\ddot{q} \quad (3.18)$$

where q is the displacement of the structure in the wave's direction. C_a represents the added mass coefficient and C_d represents the drag coefficient. Both are readily obtained from databooks for horizontal flows across cylinders. Using Morison's equation makes the model very adaptable to different platform configurations, while the WAMIT outputs are only valid for the OC4 semi submersible as it is given in [58].

A major drawback of Morison's equation in the frequency domain is the non-linearity introduced by the drag term. The dependency on \dot{q}^2 must be linearised in order to fit drag into the linear damping

matrix C. Borgman suggests the following approximation [10]:

$$|(u - \dot{q})| (u - \dot{q}) = \sqrt{\frac{8}{\pi}} \sigma_{u-\dot{q}} (u - \dot{q}) \quad (3.19)$$

The mean value $\sigma_{u-\dot{q}}$ shown above is obtained from the property of PSD curves shown in equation 3.9:

$$\sigma_{u-\dot{q}}^2 = \int_{\omega=0}^{\omega_N} S_{(u-\dot{q})(u-\dot{q})} d\omega \quad (3.20)$$

The PSD of relative velocity is obtained using a similar equation to equation 3.12, where the transfer function represents the relative velocity magnitude per unit wave height and $S_{\eta\eta}(\omega)$ is the PSD of wave heights.

$$\sigma_{u-\dot{q}}^2 = \int_{\omega=0}^{\omega_N} \left| \underbrace{\omega e^{-k\frac{z_b}{2}} e^{-ikx}}_{\text{wave velocity } u \text{ at mid-depth}} - \underbrace{i\omega(x_1(\omega) - \frac{z_b}{2}\theta_1(\omega))}_{\text{platform velocity } \dot{q} \text{ at mid-depth}} \right|^2 S_{\eta\eta}(\omega) d\omega \quad (3.21)$$

Note that $\sigma_{u-\dot{q}}^2$ is dependent on platform motions x_1 and θ_1 which themselves depend on drag force. The equation of motion must therefore be solved by iteration until convergence of the solutions is reached. This comes at a computational cost which should be taken into account when considering whether or not to include drag forces in the model. The drag component of Morison's equation can also separately be added to the results of potential theory if viscous drag turns out to be of importance.

Choosing the relevant theory

As specified in section 3.2.1, the platform will undergo a range of sea states throughout its lifetime, so that the structure could vary from comparatively small to large. A summary of the hydrodynamic forces to consider is provided in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2 Hydrodynamic forces acting on body

Hydrodynamic force	Description	Relevance
Drag force	Arises from vortex shedding and flow separation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small bodies
Diffraction force	Forces from waves on fixed body (external excitation forces).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Large bodies: panel method • Small bodies: inertia coefficient $C_m = 1 + C_a$
Radiation force	Forces on moving body in calm water (added mass +damping effect)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Large bodies: both added mass and damping from panel method • Small bodies: only added mass with added mass coefficient C_a

A good indicator of flow separation is the Keulegan-Carpenter(KC) number, which represents the drag to inertia force ratio on a structure and therefore gives an indication on whether the flow is separated or not.

$$KC = \frac{uT_p}{D} \quad (3.22)$$

where u is the depth-dependent velocity amplitude of the wave which can be derived from T_p using table 3.1. T_p is the wave period and D is the diameter of the structure.

For values of KC above 2, the flow becomes separated and Morison's equation must be used, while below 2 potential theory is valid. [39] gives an approximate classification of sea states from mild to extreme shown in Table 3.3, for which the KC values can be calculated along one of the platform's offset cylinders.

Table 3.3 Fully developed sea state test cases [39]

Sea State	Period T_p (in s)	Average wave height H (in m)
Sea State 1 (mild)	3.2	0.33
Sea State 2	4.6	0.88
Sea State 3	6.2	1.8
Sea State 4	7.7	3.2
Sea State 5	9.9	5.1
Sea State 6	10.8	7.4
Sea State 7	12.4	10.3
Sea State 8 (extreme)	13.9	13.9

The corresponding KC values displayed in Figure 3.6 are obtained along one of the offset cylinders using the equations given in Table 3.1 to derive the wave velocity u as a function of (H , T_p) and depth.

Fig. 3.6 KC values along one of the offset cylinders [26]

The sudden change in values is due to the change in geometry as the heave plates are reached. It appears that except for the harshest weather conditions, the KC value stays below the flow-separation threshold. As these extreme conditions are relatively rare, they will play a small part in the fatigue life of the structure and therefore a non-separated flow, i.e. potential flow theory, is considered adequate for this study.

3.2.3 Hydrodynamic forces on platform

The use of linear potential-flow wave theory for modelling wave-structure interaction has several implications. The linearity allows to analyse the effect of each frequency separately and to eventually combine the results. It also allows to separate the problem into forces caused by waves on a fixed structure (diffraction forces) and forces on a moving structure in calm water (radiation forces). Diffraction forces are complex valued and must therefore be represented by a magnitude and a phase. The WAMIT results provided by Jonkman et al. [58] for unit amplitude diffraction forces on the OC4 semi-submersible at each frequency are shown below.

Fig. 3.7 Frequency dependent magnitude and phase of diffraction forces per unit wave amplitude (Data provided by Masciola, co-author of [58])

An interesting observation from plots a) and c) is that the surge and pitch wave forces per unit wave amplitude are most prominent between 0 and 0.2Hz and dominated by two peaks and a trough. This can be linked to the geometry of the structure compared to the wave length of the incoming waves. From Table 3.1 a direct relationship is drawn between wave number k and wave frequency ω in deep waters:

$$k = \frac{\omega^2}{g} \quad (3.23)$$

The distance between two offset columns of the platform in the x direction is $\Delta x = 43.3m$. Waves having a wave length equal to this distance or a submultiple of it will hit the columns in phase while wave lengths of twice this distance will be out of phase by 180° . This is illustrated in Figure 3.8.

Fig. 3.8 Influence of wave length on diffraction forces

Morison's equation, while not used here, is useful to understand the influence of wave velocity u on the wave forces. In Morison's equation, the inertial component F_I of horizontal wave loads depends on \dot{u} . The surge force will be the sum of the F_{I_i} on each column. The pitch force will be the sum of moments about reference point P, arising from each F_{I_i} and the dynamic pressure at the bottom of each cylinder.

From Figure 3.8, it is clear that in-phase wave velocities result in higher contributions to surge and pitch from F_I , while out of phase wave velocities result in higher pitch contributions from dynamic pressure at the bottom of each cylinder. This is made clear by the peaks and troughs pointed out in Figures 3.7a and 3.7c corresponding to wave lengths of Δx and $2\Delta x$. As the pitch force is a

combination of in-phase and out-of phase phenomena, the peaks are slightly shifted from the purely in-phase and purely out-of-phase peaks. The peak at 0.1Hz for the pitch forces corresponds to waves long enough that an optimal ratio is met between in-phase and out-of-phase forces. Note that for low frequencies, surge and pitch forces are out of phase by 180° as shown by figures b.) and d.).

This dependence of wave forces on geometry leads to additional peaks in the response function which are not associated with the natural frequencies of any degree of freedom. Moreover, these diffraction results assume a unit amplitude wave at each frequency and must be multiplied by the wave spectrum to represent realistic wave forces. As Figure 3.5 in section 3.2.1 shows, it turns out most wave spectra have their peak frequency between 0.07 and 0.2Hz. This implies that the peaks observed in Figure 3.7 will be further amplified and clear response peaks are to be expected close to these diffraction peaks.

This underlines a first weak point in the semi submersible's design. Generally offshore structures are designed to have their surge and pitch natural frequencies outside of the main wave frequency range to avoid having response peaks close to excitation peaks. While this is also the case for the OC4 semi submersible (as will be shown later on), the geometry of the structure still causes waves frequencies to have a large impact on the structure's behaviour.

Radiation forces, caused by the motion of a structure in a body of water, are another part of the potential theory analysis. These can be expressed as a function of two parameters, added mass and radiation damping, which are scalar values that are respectively added to the mass matrix \mathbf{M} and the damping matrix \mathbf{C} in the EOM. Again, the values are obtained from [58] and presented in Figure 3.9.

(a) Surge added mass $A(1,1)$

(b) Surge radiation damping $B(1,1)$

(c) Surge-pitch coupling added mass $A(1,2)=A(2,1)$

(d) Surge-pitch coupling radiation damping $B(1,2)=B(2,1)$

(e) Pitch added mass $A(2,2)$

(f) Pitch radiation damping $B(2,2)$

Fig. 3.9 Frequency dependent parameters obtained from radiation forces per unit wave amplitude (Data provided by Masciola, co-author of [58])

Whether for surge, pitch or coupling between the two, the added mass does not change much with frequency. An constant average value was therefore taken for the model. Radiation damping

on the other hand shows high values close to the wave frequency region but is almost negligible at lower frequencies. Hydrodynamic damping will therefore not be involved in low frequency motions.

3.2.4 Hydrostatic and mooring forces

Hydrostatic stability of the floating system should be a first check before running the model, especially once TMDs cause additional masses to be spread throughout the structure.

Buoyancy stability

A first limit to TMD masses is set by vertical buoyancy: the mass of the structure determines the draft of the platform and therefore also the clearance above still water level (SWL). The clearance between the still water level (SWL) and the parts of the structure not design for wave loads (in this case the tower) should be of 1.5m above the 50-year return period maximum wave crest [1]. In the middle of the North Sea, the 50-year return period maximum crest heights are around 12m above SWL [33]. This implies a deck clearance of at least 13.5m above SWL, which is not even met by the original OC4 semi submersible which has a deck clearance of $H_c = 10m$. While these measures might be extremely conservative as they are meant for ultimate limit state design, they still indicate that the immersion depth of the platform from adding TMDs to the structure cannot be increased too much if safe clearance is to be provided. An additional 2m of immersion is allowed in this model for the mass of the TMDs. Considering this is taken up by the extra buoyancy of the offset columns, this allows for an additional TMD mass of $703.5 * 10^3 kg$, which represents 5% of the platform-tower-RNA mass. Previous studies considered TMD masses between 0.2% and 5% of the structural mass [45], so this can be considered a reasonable upper bound.

Pitch stability

Another aspect of hydrostatics is pitch stability. This is determined by the metacentric height GM of the floating system. When the structure is in motion, its centre of buoyancy is displaced as the platform tilts. The point of intersection of the vertical through the displaced centre of buoyancy with the line passing through the undisplaced centre of buoyancy and the centre of gravity (which remains fixed) corresponds to the metacentre M. If M is located above the centre of mass G, the system has a positive metacentric height and is considered stable as gravity acts as a restoring moment. If M is below G, the system is unstable as gravity acts as an overturning moment. This is summarised in Figure 3.10. Note that mooring lines righting moments are ignored for hydrostatic stability checks, as is advised by [1].

Fig. 3.10 Pitch stability of floating body [15]

Referring to Figure 3.10, it appears that GM can be expressed as $GM = BM - BG$. BM depends on the second moment of area I_{xx} of the waterplane and the immersed volume V_0 , as shown below:

$$BM = \frac{I_{xx}}{V_0} \quad (3.24)$$

Therefore:

$$GM = \frac{I_{xx}}{V_0} - BG \quad (3.25)$$

The larger GM , the bigger the restoring moment will be. For a given immersed volume, this is where the geometry of the semi-submersible has an advantage over other platforms in terms of pitch stability due to its large second moment of area.

Metacentre and reference system

From the definition of the metacentre, point M can be considered fixed during a floating body's rotation. This is important when considering the reference frame under which Lagrange's equation of motion is set up. All the data provided in Figures 3.7 and 3.9 is obtained with respect to the centre point P at SWL (see Figure 3.1) assuming an inertial frame of reference [37]. However, during pitch motion of the platform point P itself will rotate about point M , resulting in a horizontal motion of the reference point P (assuming small angular displacements). D'Alembert's principle of inertial forces allows to transform an accelerating rigid body into its static equivalent by adding inertial forces acting at the centre of mass. The equation of motion of the FOWT will therefore be solved about P , to which a horizontal translational inertial force is added due to the rotation of P about M and the surge motion of the FOWT as a whole with respect to an inertial frame of reference.

Mooring lines

Mooring lines for a semi submersible have a catenary shape depending on their own weight, buoyancy and the distance between their anchoring points. In the undisplaced configuration part of the anchors rests on the seabed and doesn't contribute to tension in the line. The force created by the anchors' tension on the FOWT in the undisplaced configuration is modelled as additional weight increasing the platform draft by another 0.5m.

As the platform moves, the anchor's length resting on the seabed changes and consequently the tension in the line varies as well. This geometric stiffness, on top of elastic stiffness, induces non-linearities at larger displacements. This study has assumed a linear stiffness for the mooring cables. The validity of this assumption is tested against results from [58], where mooring forces are obtained from surge and pitch motions of the OC4 semi-submersible in 200m deep waters, as shown in Figure 3.11.

Fig. 3.11 Mooring lines restoring forces from surge and pitch displacement [58]

Pitch motion shows a very linear relationship, which validates the assumption in this study. On the other hand, surge clearly causes non-linear and asymmetric responses above 10m displacements. The asymmetry is caused by the geometric configuration of the platform as three cylinders.

When using linear stiffness parameters, the platform surge displacements caused by wind turbulence and wave forces are well below the 10m threshold, as will be seen later on. However the constant wind force on the rotor can result in a mean displacement of several meters along the x-axis. For the maximum thrust load on the turbine, the model with linear stiffness outputs a mean x-axis displacement of 13m. This is still within a reasonable range to consider the restoring force as linear. Moreover, most of the time the thrust load will be lower, making a linear stiffness assumption acceptable.

3.2.5 Second order and low frequency effects

Wave loads were assumed to be purely linear so that results at separate frequencies could be superimposed to find the total loading on the structure. In reality waves at different frequencies interact with each other and result in non-linear terms. These are generally much smaller than first-order forces [53], however second-order wave forces can be relevant for semi-submersible structures and will be discussed briefly.

The second-order interactions between wave frequencies result in difference frequency loads ($\omega_i - \omega_j$, also called drift loads and causing low frequency excitations) and sum frequency loads ($\omega_i + \omega_j$, causing high frequency excitations) [53]. Considering the low natural frequencies of floating platforms, only wave drift loads can have a significant impact. In traditional offshore engineering wave drift loads would have to be taken into account. However for FOWTs this loading at low frequencies is overshadowed by low-frequency wind forces, as will be seen in section 3.3. It was therefore decided to ignore second order wave loads in this model.

The low-frequency wind loads will induce low frequency motion of the structure. At low frequencies, radiation damping is barely present as shown in Figure 3.9 and viscous drag damping is negligible, as explained in the previous section. This could leave the structure with very little damping in this region. However two other damping sources play a major role at low frequencies (<0.05Hz): wave drift damping and mooring line damping [55]. The former arises from the change in wave drift force caused by the relative motion of the platform. The latter is caused by hydrodynamic drag forces on the mooring lines as they are displaced underwater [55].

Model test data of the OC4 semi-submersible shows that drift damping at low frequencies should be around 6% of critical damping [29]. This is more conservative than the 20% suggested by [16] for low frequencies combining wave drift and mooring damping. A constant drift damping of $0.06 * c_{critical}$ is therefore set for low frequencies in this model.

3.3 Aerodynamics

This study will only focus on the thrust component of aerodynamic loads as only the fore-aft motion of the FOWT is considered. The state-of-the-art software calculating wind turbine aerodynamic forces operate in the time domain. This is partly because thrust forces have a highly non-linear dependence on squared relative wind velocity W_r , as shown below:

$$F_T = \frac{1}{2} C_T(W_r) \rho_{air} A W_r^2 \quad (3.26)$$

C_T is the turbine's thrust coefficient, W_r depends on incoming wind speed and the structural motion. Linearisation methods have been developed for aerodynamic loading and show acceptable behaviour as long as abrupt transient gusts are avoided and fluctuation amplitudes of the angle of attack stay small (below 3°) [49]. In this model the aerodynamic effects are split into three components: the steady mean wind loads, the turbulence induced loads and the aerodynamic damping

3.3.1 Steady wind loads

The Blade Element Momentum (BEM) theory can reasonably be applied for operations in steady winds [46]. Each turbine blade is divided into sections, forces on each section are obtained from 2D airfoil theory as explained below and the total forces are obtained by summing up the contribution of each section. The thrust force on the turbine as a function of wind velocity must be calculated separately from the main model and then supplied as data to the equation of motion in the model.

The loss of axial momentum and gain in angular momentum of the airflow as it passes a blade section are represented by axial and tangential induction factors represented in Figure 3.13 by a and a' . The values of a and a' influence the inflow angle ϕ , which in turns affects the angle of attack $\alpha = \phi - \theta$, where θ is the twist angle of the blade. a and a' themselves depend on C_l and C_d , which in turn depend on α . Therefore an iterative method is required until converging values of a and a' are found. The thrust contribution from that blade section can then be found as follows:

$$\delta T = \frac{1}{2} \rho_{air} W^2 B c (C_l \cos \phi + C_d \sin \phi) \quad (3.27)$$

Fig. 3.12 2D aerofoil aerodynamics [62]

The airfoil profiles, chord lengths c and twist angles θ along the blades are taken from the 5MW NREL reference turbine [37]. The blade profiles vary along the blade from cylinders at the root to DU (Delft University) profiles and NACA profiles. For each airfoil, the C_l and C_d values will vary non-linearly as a function of the angle of attack, particularly when the blades are close to stalling conditions. Jonkman et al. [37] provide C_d and C_l curves accounting for several corrections, including tip loss due to 3D flow and dynamic stall caused by a delay in separation-point movement

when the blades are stalled, which has a hysteretic effect [49]. An example is given below for the NACA64 airfoil.

Fig. 3.13 Lift and drag coefficients of NACA64 airfoil [37]

Jonkman et al. [37] also specify the variation of rotational velocity with wind speed. With this information, the thrust force as a function of wind speed can be obtained from BEM theory, as shown by the blue curve in Figure 3.14.

Fig. 3.14 Rotor thrust force under steady wind conditions (red curve from Jonkman et al. [37])

The red thrust curve shows good agreement with the BEM theory at low wind velocities. At 11m/s, which corresponds to the rated wind speed, the two curves start differing considerably. This is caused by the pitch control mechanism which kicks in to maintain the power output of the turbine constant and therefore reduces the thrust on the turbine. As control mechanisms are highly non-linear they are not directly modeled in this study. However for above-rated wind speeds Jonkman's results will be used for steady wind thrust forces.

The steady thrust force is used to determine the static displacement of the turbine. The force $Q_i(\omega)$ at each DOF is determined using the virtual work method outlined in section 3.1.1. The DOF

displacements are then obtained by:

$$\mathbf{x}_{\text{stat}}(\omega) = \mathbf{K}^{-1}(\omega)\mathbf{Q}(\omega) \quad (3.28)$$

The bending moment at the tower base caused by these displacements is important to consider in combination with the dynamic fatigue stress cycles.

3.3.2 Aerodynamic damping

The tower and platform motion will modify the relative wind speed perceived by the rotor at hub height. This causes a change in angle of attack which in turn affects the lift force on the blades and the resulting thrust on the rotor, as shown in Figure 3.15.

Fig. 3.15 Mechanism of aerodynamic damping [46]

A basic linearisation of aerodynamic damping was derived by Garrad [60] assuming fixed-speed and fixed-pitch turbines below stall conditions. The derivation is covered in detail in Appendix B and the result is shown in equation 3.29.

$$dT = \frac{B\rho\omega}{2} \int_{R_0}^R C_L' c r dr (\Delta u - \dot{x}) = c_a (\Delta u - \dot{x}) \quad (3.29)$$

dT : change in thrust force

c_a : aerodynamic damping coefficient

Δu : change in incoming wind speed

\dot{x} : velocity of the rotor

Switching the $-c_a\dot{x}$ term to the other side of the equation of motion makes it contribute to the damping matrix. Van der Tempel and Salzmann simplified and generalised this result by claiming

that for varying speed turbines the aerodynamic damping could be derived as:

$$c_a = \frac{dT}{dU} \quad (3.30)$$

As the thrust curve is provided in Figure 3.14 as a function of wind speed, this should be readily obtained. However complications arise above the rated wind speed limit as interaction with the non-linear pitch control mechanism occurs. If the feedback frequency of the control mechanism is fast enough, the blades will adapt to the incoming wind velocity quickly enough to follow the red curve in Figure 3.14. As the slope of the thrust curve is negative above rated wind speeds, this would imply negative damping. If the wind variations are too fast, the blades will not change pitch in time and the change in thrust will not follow the slope of the red curve.

Aerodynamic damping of pitch-controlled wind turbines is therefore very dependent on a non-linear control mechanism which is hard to model in the frequency domain. It is nonetheless very important to model aerodynamic damping accurately as it can be one of the main contributors to damping of the floating system in certain frequency ranges, particularly near the pitch resonance frequency, as shown in Figure 3.22. It is also the only parameter which causes turbine operation to interact with structural dynamics, which prevents wind and wave excitations to be treated as fully independent phenomena [60].

It was therefore decided to use the aerodynamic damping values as a function of free-flow wind speed given in [24] from time domain simulations of the 5MW NREL rotor dynamics. Aerodynamic damping values as a function of wind speed are shown in Figure 3.16, expressed as a ratio relative to the tower's critical damping. Note that these results also account for the flapwise deflection of the blades which isn't modeled explicitly in the simplified model presented.

Fig. 3.16 Final aerodynamic damping values used (data taken from [24])

For a specific wind speed, aerodynamic damping is treated as a constant which is added to structural and hydrodynamic damping. While this limits the generality of the simulations to a specific wind turbine model, it allows for a more accurate understanding of the effect of tuned mass dampers compared to other damping mechanisms in the FOWT system.

The fact that neither the thrust force nor the aerodynamic damping coefficient are monotonically increasing with wind velocity implies that increasing wind velocities are not always detrimental for the turbine and could have stabilising properties in some cases.

3.3.3 Turbulence

The wind turbulence in this model will consist only of freestream wind speed variations assuming the FOWT system doesn't interact with any upstream wind turbines. Wind speed variations can arise from topographic and atmospheric variability and their spectral density distribution will depend on the probability distribution of the wind speed variations [11]. Wind turbulence is generally represented by a stationary random zero-mean Gaussian distribution [12]. In this model the Kaimal spectrum was chosen to represent the frequency distribution of turbulent wind speeds, with the assumption of purely axial wind variation acting uniformly over the whole rotor area. The expression for the Kaimal power density spectrum was taken from [12] and shown in Equation 3.31.

$$S_1(f) = \frac{4 \frac{L_1}{V_{hub}}}{\left(1 + 6f \frac{L_1}{V_{hub}}\right)^{\frac{5}{3}}} \sigma_1^2 \quad (3.31)$$

where f is the frequency in Hz, L_1 is the integral scale parameter which represents the length scale of the turbulence phenomenon and depends on hub height, and σ_1 is the turbulent horizontal velocity standard deviation which can be obtained as follows:

$$\sigma_1 = I_{ref}(0.75V_{hub} + 5.6)$$

I_{ref} is the turbulence intensity and depends on local turbulence conditions. Out at sea, wind turbulence is usually lower than onshore as there are less obstructions to free-flowing winds [2]. A constant value of 0.1 is therefore taken for the turbulence intensity.

Taylor's frozen turbulence hypothesis is also considered valid. It assumes that for moderate turbulence levels, wind speed variations can be attributed to the convection of a constant spatial pattern across a point at a mean velocity U [66]. Therefore turbulent wind speed in our case can be expressed as:

$$u(x, y_1, z_1, t) = u(x, y_2, z_2, t) = u(x - Ut, y_1, z_1, 0)$$

where (y_1, z_1) and (y_2, z_2) represent two different points in the plane of the rotor and $U = V_{hub}$. The spatial independence of turbulence is acceptable as long as the turbulent eddies are of a much

larger scale than the turbine diameter. The Kaimal spectrum shown in Figure 3.17 shows that most of the turbulence energy is located below 0.05Hz. This implies large time periods and therefore also large length scales, making spatial independence acceptable.

The resulting Kaimal spectrum is shown in Figure 3.17 for a wind hub velocity of 10m/s.

Fig. 3.17 Kaimal turbulence power spectral density for mean wind speeds of 10m/s

Clearly, most of the turbulent energy lies at low frequencies. In section 3.2.5, it was shown that the floating wind turbine system had little damping at low frequencies. The wind loads could therefore have a substantial impact on the platform motion at low frequencies.

A final step is to translate the wind velocity spectrum into wind loads at hub height through a transfer function. Wind loading depends on a variety of non-linear factors which are hard to model in the frequency domain. The current study being done for feasibility assessment purposes rather than detailed design, adapted results from previous papers are considered satisfactory.

In [68], a frequency domain transfer function between wind speeds and hub loads is obtained from time simulations in *Bladed* on 2MW Vestas V66 turbines. Tempel and Vries consider the rotor to be clamped at the hub to uncouple turbine calculations from support structure dynamics. While the software takes into account many non-linear factors such as tip loss corrections, wake influence and tower shadow, the effect of wind shear is essential to understand the result shown in Figure 3.18. Wind shear causes an exponential increase in wind speeds with height, which results in oscillating loads on the blades as they rotate through this varying wind field. For a three-bladed turbine, a loading peak therefore arises at three times the mean rotor speed Ω .

Fig. 3.18 Wind loading transfer function for 2MW Vestas rotor [68]

The Vestas turbines have a mean rotor speed of $\Omega = 0.35\text{Hz}$, which explains the peak near 1Hz shown in Figure 3.18. To scale this transfer function to a 5MW NREL turbine with a rated rotor speed of 0.211Hz, [70] suggests a linear scaling of the y-axis by the power ratio of the two turbines and a linear scaling of the x-axis by the rotational speed ratio. The resulting transfer functions for each turbine are shown below.

Fig. 3.19 Wind loading transfer function for two different rotors (data taken from [68] and [70])

The wind turbulence load spectrum is then obtained by multiplying the squared transfer function by the Kaimal spectrum, in a similar way to the wave loads:

$$S_{ff} = |\mathbf{q}_{\text{wind}}(\omega)|^2 \mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{K}\mathbf{K}}(\omega) \quad (3.32)$$

While the transfer function's peak lies at 0.6Hz, most of the turbulence energy lies at much lower frequencies. Therefore turbulence shouldn't make hub loads resonate much in this frequency range. The force transfer function does however increase at very small frequencies, which could lead to considerable turbine response if it isn't damped appropriately, especially since the platform's natural frequencies are in this range. The final contribution of wind to fatigue will depend on the relative number of wind load cycles compared to wave loads which have a higher frequency and therefore could be much more damaging.

Conclusions for aerodynamics

Whether static wind thrust, aerodynamic damping or turbulence, it appears that the non-linearities involved are too complex to model directly in the frequency domain. The constant wind thrust and damping coefficient seem mainly dependent on the upstream wind velocity and can therefore be derived separately as a function of upstream wind velocity before being added to the EOM. In this case, results from the literature were taken. For wind turbulence, the transfer function was also obtained from the literature from Fourier transformations of time-domain results. Turbulence results more specific to the studied turbine could be obtained, however these first approximations are considered enough as further sections will show atmospheric turbulence is not the main contributor to tower base fatigue.

3.4 Combining the different parts

Figure 3.20 provides a summary of the way the different forces presented in the previous sections affect the floating turbine's dynamics.

Fig. 3.20 Summary of the factors affecting the EOM

Now that the different factors contributing to the equation of motion have been explained, the matrices used in the model can be derived in more detail. As mentioned in section 3.2.4, the EOM is solved with reference to point P, but with the addition of inertial forces due to horizontal motion of P itself caused by surge and rotation about the metacentre.

3.4.1 Implementing Lagrange's equation of motion

The kinetic energy of the FOWT system consists therefore of the following terms:

$$T = \frac{1}{2}(I_p + A_r)\dot{\theta}_1^2 + \frac{1}{2}I_t\dot{\theta}_2^2 + \frac{1}{2}m_t(\dot{x}_1 + MC_t \sin\dot{\theta}_1)^2 + \frac{1}{2}(m_p + A_t)(\dot{x}_1 + MC_p \sin\dot{\theta}_1)^2 \quad (3.33)$$

The terms in the equation 3.33 are explained in table 3.4.

Table 3.4 Explanation of variables in kinetic energy equation

A_r and A_t	Added mass from pitch and surge
	Platform mass moment of inertia with respect to P
I_p	$I_p = I_{cm_p} + m_p R_p^2$
	Tower mass moment of inertia with respect to tower base T_t
I_t	$I_t = I_{cm_t} + m_t R_{tower}^2$
MC_t	Distance between metacentre and tower base
MC_p	Distance between metacentre and platform centre of mass

Note that cross-coupling added mass terms only arise after differentiating T with respect to each DOF. DOFs θ_1 and θ_2 both represent rotations in the general coordinate system, so that the angle difference between the tower and the platform is obtained by subtracting the two ($\Delta\theta_{base} = \theta_1 - \theta_2$). The mass matrix M is obtained by differentiating T with respect to x_1 , $\dot{\theta}_1$ and $\dot{\theta}_2$ and assuming small angular displacements (see Appendix A).

As the additional inertial forces are taken into account by T, the potential energy function V can be derived with respect to P, except for the mooring line stiffness which depends on the relative motion with respect to the inertial frame of the seabed:

$$V = K_{moor}(x_1, \theta_1) + \frac{1}{2}K_{hydrostat}\theta_1^2 + \frac{1}{2}K_{tower}(\theta_1 - \theta_2)^2 - m_p g \cos(\theta_1)R_p + m_t g (R_{tower} \cos(\theta_2) + H_c \cos(\theta_1)) \quad (3.34)$$

The terms in equation 3.34 are explained in table 3.5.

Table 3.5 Explanation of variables in potential energy equation

$K_{moor}(x_1, \theta_1)$	Linearised mooring stiffness (from [57])
$K_{hydrostat}$	Hydrostatic restoring stiffness from buoyancy only (gravity considered separately)
K_{tower}	Linearised tower-platform connection stiffness
H_c	Distance between sea surface at P and tower base
m_p dependent term	Potential energy from platform height with respect to P
m_t dependent term	Potential energy from tower height with respect to P

Again, the stiffness matrix \mathbf{K} is derived by differentiating V with respect to x_1 , θ_1 and θ_2 . Finally, the work done by the structure from the damping terms can be expressed as follows:

$$W_D = \frac{1}{2}D_{tower}(\dot{\theta}_1 - \dot{\theta}_2)^2 + D_{hydro}(x_1, \dot{\theta}_1) + \frac{1}{2}D_{drift}x_1^2 + \frac{1}{2}c_a(x_1 + H_c\dot{\theta}_1 + R_{hub}\dot{\theta}_2)^2 \quad (3.35)$$

The terms in equation 3.35 are explained in table 3.6.

Table 3.6 Explanation of variables in damping term

D_{tower}	Linear structural damping at tower base
$D_{hydro}(x_1, \dot{\theta}_1)$	Radiation damping (from [57])
D_{drift}	Drift damping taken as 6% of critical damping in surge only
c_a	Linearised aerodynamic damping (see Appendix B)

The damping forces are obtained by differentiating W_D with respect to x_1 , $\dot{\theta}_1$ and $\dot{\theta}_2$. Note that drag forces have been left out for these initial computations as their effects are minor while their computational cost is quite significant. Additionally, unlike stiffness and inertia forces, damping is frequency dependent due to the radiation damping term. Once the \mathbf{M} , $\mathbf{C}(\omega)$ and \mathbf{K} matrices have been derived, the structure's transfer function $\mathbf{H}(\omega)$ is obtained.

The influence of external forces (wind and wave forces) on each DOF is obtained from the principal of virtual work, as outlined in section 3.1.1 with P taken as a reference point.

For wind turbulence, the result Q_{wind} for a unit amplitude wind velocity is as follows:

$$q_{wind}(\omega) = f_{wind}(\omega) \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ H_c \\ R_{hub} \end{pmatrix}$$

where $f_{wind}(\omega)$ is given by Figure 3.18.

The wave diffraction forces per unit wave amplitude taken from [57] are given with respect to P, therefore there is no coupling between the surge and pitch wave forces. Taking into account the magnitude and phase plots given in Figure 3.7 the wave forces on the structure per unit wave amplitude are:

$$q_{wave}(\omega) = \begin{pmatrix} f_{surge}(\omega)e^{i\phi_{surge}(\omega)} \\ f_{pitch}(\omega)e^{i\phi_{pitch}(\omega)} \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

The actual frequency distribution of wave and wind forces on the structure is obtained by multiplying the unit amplitude forces by the wave height/wind velocity at each frequency, given by their respective spectrum:

$$Q_{wind} = q_{wind}(\omega) * u(\omega) \quad (3.36)$$

$$Q_{wave} = q_{wave}(\omega) * \eta(\omega) \quad (3.37)$$

However, $u(\omega)$ and $\eta(\omega)$ are not readily available and for given site conditions these environmental parameters are usually given as power spectrum density functions. The FOWT's response is therefore first calculated as a response amplitude operator (RAO) before being multiplied by each parameter's power spectrum density function to obtain the FOWT's power spectrum density response function. The response amplitude operator (RAO) represents the response of the FOWT to a unit wave height/wind speed input at each frequency. It is the transfer function between the wave heights/wind speeds and the structure's motions and is obtained as shown below:

$$\mathbf{x}_{wave}(\omega) = \mathbf{H}^{-1}(\omega)\mathbf{q}_{wave}(\omega) = \begin{pmatrix} x_{1_{wave}} \\ \theta_{1_{wave}} \\ \theta_{2_{wave}} \\ \vdots \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{x}_{wind}(\omega) = \mathbf{H}^{-1}(\omega)\mathbf{q}_{wind}(\omega) = \begin{pmatrix} x_{1_{wind}} \\ \theta_{1_{wind}} \\ \theta_{2_{wind}} \\ \vdots \end{pmatrix}$$

$\mathbf{q}_{wave}(\omega)$ and $\mathbf{H}(\omega)$ are complex valued, which implies a magnitude and phase for the response.

3.4.2 Model validation for wave excitations

The RAOs derived above are obtained by solving the EOM using MATLAB. The wave-excited RAO magnitudes of the OC4 semisubmersible for surge and pitch have also been obtained by [7] assuming linear wave theory and ignoring any aerodynamic interaction effects. Using the same constraints on the model set up in this study, results show good agreement, as shown in Figure 3.21. The displayed RAOs are in absolute values.

Fig. 3.21 Comparison of platform RAOs with results from [7]

To obtain relevant results it is particularly important that the models agree between 0.08Hz and 0.2Hz as this is the main wave forcing frequency range. The peaks in the wave diffraction forces in

Figure 3.7 are found again in the pitch RAO as a shallow peak between 0.05Hz and 0.18Hz. The platform's surge and pitch frequencies are well below the wave frequency range. The two resonance peaks observed in each figure show the interaction between surge and pitch motion. The tower's natural frequency is around 0.4Hz and is too high to affect the motion of the platform.

3.4.3 Effect of adding aerodynamics

So far the plots shown ignore the effect of aerodynamic damping, which is a significant part of damping for certain frequency ranges. When included in the model, the effect seems most significant around the natural frequency peaks of the structure:

Fig. 3.22 Effect of aerodynamic damping on platform pitch RAO

Aerodynamic damping clearly reduces peak responses, but a side effect is an increase in response between 0.05 and 0.08Hz. For environmental conditions with wave frequencies around this area, this could lead to a higher tower top displacement.

In terms of fatigue, the parameter of interest is actually the difference between the tower and platform motion. As will be shown in section 4.1.2, the moment at the base of the tower is linearly correlated with this differential movement, as the spring stiffness at the tower-platform connection is assumed constant for relatively small displacements. The impact of aerodynamic damping on the RAO of $\theta_2 - \theta_1$ for wave excitations only is shown in Figure 3.23.

Fig. 3.23 Impact of aerodynamic damping on tower-platform angle difference RAO for wave excitations only

From this graph it seems that at the wave frequency range between 0.1 and 0.2 Hz, aerodynamic damping increases the platform-tower motion discrepancy rather than decreasing it and is therefore detrimental to the FOWT's fatigue lifetime.

For fixed offshore wind turbines, aerodynamic damping was shown to be very effective against wave excitations, with significant reductions in damage equivalent loads (a metric for fatigue loading) at foundation level [24]. In this case, moments in the foundation at seabed level are more influenced by the tower motion above the SWL than by wave forces at SWL. Equation 3.35 shows that for floating platforms, aerodynamic damping has more effect on θ_2 than on θ_1 as the moment lever arm R_{hub} is bigger than H_c . Depending on the stiffness of the tower-platform connection, aerodynamic damping can therefore significantly reduce tower motion while letting the platform be more influenced by waves. Compared to monopiles where the tower and the foundation will respond in a more unified manner, aerodynamic damping can create larger differential movements for floating structures despite reducing overall tower top displacements (TTD). Indeed, the root mean squared TTD for $H_s = 2M$, $T_p = 7S$ and 10 m/s wind yields a value of 1.41 m with aerodynamic damping while it increases to 3.84 m without it.

The effect of aerodynamic damping on ocean wave response is therefore positive or negative depending on whether tower top motion or tower base loading is considered. Considering the focus of this study on fatigue loading, the detrimental effect of aerodynamic damping is an interesting property of floating turbines.

Finally, the turbulent loads F_{wind} are added to these results to obtain realistic loading conditions. The RAO outputs for wind forces are shown below:

(a) Platform pitch θ_1 RAO due to wind loading

(b) Angle difference $|\theta_2 - \theta_1|$ RAO caused by wind loading

Fig. 3.24 RAO outputs from turbulent wind forces

The wind loading transfer function in Figure 3.19 indicates that wind excitations are quite high at very low frequencies, then decrease until 0.2Hz at which point they stay at a relatively constant value until 0.5Hz. This explains the high peak at the platform pitch natural frequency at 0.05Hz. For wind loading, aerodynamic damping clearly plays a beneficial role both for displacements and fatigue. This is because in this case the tower and the platform's motion both depend on forces at rotor level, while aerodynamic damping is also a force acting at rotor level and therefore can reduce the impact of external forces more directly.

3.4.4 Overall dynamic response of FOWT

When combining the effect of wave loading, wind loading, aerodynamic damping and all the other structural and hydrodynamic properties of the FOWT, the overall response power spectral density is obtained by multiplying the RAOs for waves and wind excitations respectively by the JONSWAP and the Kaimal spectrum:

$$\mathbf{S}_{xx}(\omega) = |\mathbf{x}_{wave}|^2 S_{\eta\eta}(\omega) + |\mathbf{x}_{wind}|^2 S_{KK}(\omega) \quad (3.38)$$

An example is given below for the platform surge and pitch response for a moderate sea state ($H_s = 2m$, $T_p = 7s$ $U_{wind} = 10m/s$).

Fig. 3.25 Surge and pitch response PSD for a specific weather condition

Values at very low frequencies are governed by the Kaimal spectrum but should be considered with care as Kaimal's spectrum is only valid for 10-min intervals. This puts a lower bound of 0.002Hz on the minimum frequency used in the model. Wind turbulence seems to create a lot of resonance at platform pitch frequency. Again, the importance of the geometric resonance peak near 0.15Hz becomes apparent.

Finally, the tower top displacement power spectrum density is obtained by combining the motion of each DOF:

$$S_{tt}(\omega) = |x_{1_{wave}} + \theta_{1_{wave}} * H_c + \theta_{2_{wave}} * R_{hub}|^2 S_{\eta\eta}(\omega) + |x_{1_{wind}} + \theta_{1_{wind}} * H_c + \theta_{2_{wind}} * R_{hub}|^2 S_{KK}(\omega) \quad (3.39)$$

The root mean squared value of the tower top displacement (TTD) over the whole frequency range can be obtained from the power spectral density curve using equation 3.9.

The response spectrum for surge, platform pitch, tower pitch and tower top displacement are shown below for illustrative purposes using two different environmental conditions. $H_s = 2m$, $T_p = 7s$, $U_{wind} = 10m/s$ and $H_s = 3m$, $T_p = 12s$, $U_{wind} = 10m/s$.

Fig. 3.26 Two examples of power spectral density curves from different environmental conditions

The peak wave frequency in the JONSWAP spectrum is 0.14Hz in Figure 3.26a and 0.08Hz in Figure 3.26b, while wind loads are mainly under 0.05Hz. In both cases, the response at very low frequencies is particularly high and is caused by the exponential increase of the Kaimal spectrum in this area. However, these frequencies are too small to be of relevance for fatigue damage. The pitch natural frequency is also mainly excited by wind turbulence.

It is interesting to note that the tower top displacement is not a simple superposition of the individual DOFs. This means that the platform surge, pitch and tower pitch are out of phase for some frequencies, causing the overall tower top displacement to be reduced. While this is beneficial for displacements, it causes higher bending moments at the tower base. Finally, a response peak is present between 0.1Hz and 0.15Hz in both cases although its exact peak frequency varies. This corresponds to the diffraction related peak identified in Figure 3.7.

These power spectral densities will vary for different wind and wave conditions, so that the response peaks will correspondingly be spread over a range of frequencies. The suggested passive control system should therefore be capable of operating efficiently under such variable conditions.

Chapter 4

Fatigue behaviour improvement

4.1 Fatigue in the frequency domain

4.1.1 Background on fatigue

Fatigue failure of a component occurs due to cyclic loading of this component. The amount of cycles until failure depends on the amplitude of each cycle. The motions determined from the model established in Chapter 3 cause cyclic stresses in the structure. Under most operating conditions, the motions caused by wind and wave forces are small enough to stay in the elastic range. A linear relationship between motion and internal stress is therefore reasonable. The example taken in this report will be the bending stress at the base of the tower due to the difference in motion between the platform and the tower.

S-N curves are used to characterise the fatigue properties of a material. S-N curves for specific materials are obtained by subjecting the material to a harmonic load of amplitude S_1 until failure occurs after N_1 cycles. This is repeated for a range of amplitudes until a full fatigue curve is obtained over a range of cycles. An example for steel under different environmental conditions is shown in Figure 4.1.

Fig. 4.1 Example fatigue curves of C-Mn steel under different environmental conditions [4]

Several points can be raised from this graph. Uncorroded steel, represented by the upper dotted line, shows a fatigue limit at very high cycles. This implies that below a certain stress amplitude at constant harmonic loads the material will not fail. Secondly, corrosion seems to have a considerable impact on fatigue behaviour as it reduces the cycles to failure and in general eliminates the fatigue limit, implying that materials could even fail at relatively small amplitudes. Indeed, the surface damage caused by corrosion will create pits which act as stress concentrators and considerably reduce the duration of crack initiation and growth [61].

If the deck clearance requirement is respected, the platform-tower connection will stay out of range of the corrosive sea water environment for most of the time. This is why it is important to limit further platform immersion by restricting the mass of TMDs added to the structure. Additionally, an anti-corrosion protection coating is usually applied to components operating in marine conditions. Therefore the assumption of operation in non-corrosive conditions is acceptable for the tower base and no further environmental reduction factors need to be applied to the steel fatigue parameters.

So far, these conclusions apply for constant amplitude loading. To understand the difference with variable amplitude loading, the fatigue mechanism must first roughly be understood. Fatigue life is generally split between a crack nucleation (or initiation) period and a crack propagation period [61]. While the crack propagation can occur even at the smallest amplitudes, a minimum amplitude is first required to initiate the crack nucleation [61]. This explains the fatigue limit observed in Figure 4.1 for uncorroded steel.

For variable loads, the material will be subjected to a range of stress amplitudes. Traditionally this

is accounted for with the Palmgren-Miner rule, which assumes a linear cumulative damage:

$$D = \sum_{i=1}^m \frac{n_i}{N(i)} \quad (4.1)$$

where m is the number of different loading amplitudes, $N(i)$ is the cycles to failure at each amplitude based on the S-N curve and n_i is the actual number of cycles undergone at each amplitude during loading. When D reaches 1, the material fails. According to equation 4.1, loads below the fatigue limit are ignored since in that case $N = \infty$. However this fails to account for the sequential nature of loading, where larger loads can initiate cracking and smaller loads can propagate the crack [61]. Additionally, fatigue damage will depend on crack tip plasticity, local strain hardening and residual stresses which all depend on the damage caused at previous cycles through what is called the sequence effect [61]. Variable amplitude loading fatigue life is therefore hard to predict without running service-simulation fatigue tests. As this is not accessible for this project, model simplifications proposed in the literature will be taken.

4.1.2 Estimating structural lifetime

At high cycle fatigue, when amplitudes are below the yield stress and above the fatigue limit, the Basquin relation shown below is applicable.

$$N(s) = Cs^{-k} \quad (4.2)$$

where C and k are material properties.

The lifetime's exponential dependence on stress amplitude underlines the great gains in fatigue life that can be achieved by only small stress reductions. On the other hand, it also makes results very sensitive to the chosen fatigue parameters, which unfortunately rely on a range of factors such as material quality, type of connection and workmanship quality, which are hard to include in a model. The connection between the tower base and the platform is assumed to consist of bolted steel. Due to the many parameters to take into account, the literature gives a whole range of values for such connections, which ensues in widely varying fatigue lifetimes. However, once TMDs are applied (see section 4.3.1), fatigue lifetime improvements do show some agreement when expressed in relative terms rather than absolute terms. This is illustrated in Table 4.1 when comparing results from the model for a 100ton TMD installed at the bottom of the platform with a 88 000 N/m stiffness and a 9600 N/(m/s) damping coefficient. This configuration is just used as an example and the methodology to obtain fatigue lifetime is explained in the rest of this section.

Table 4.1 Comparison of fatigue properties

	Steel 1 [27]	Steel 2 [22]
C	$5.248 * 10^{12}$	$1.253 * 10^{13}$
k	3	3.1
Baseline fatigue lifetime	30.19 years	49.60 years
Fatigue lifetime with $m_{TMD} = 100ton$	30.74 years	50.53 years
Relative improvement in fatigue lifetime	1.82%	1.87%

In absolute terms, fatigue lifetimes show great variation despite only minor parameter changes, whereas relative improvements are similar. Fatigue lifetime improvements will therefore be expressed in relative terms for the rest of this study. The properties of Material 1 will be used in the model, as it yields fatigue lifetimes which are in agreement with standard design lifetimes.

As explained in the previous section, steel used in an offshore environment under variable loads will not have a fatigue limit. To account for this, [61] suggests to extend Basquin's relation into the fatigue limit domain.

Assuming the spectrum represents a stationary Gaussian random narrow banded process (where each peak corresponds to a zero-crossing), the average damage \bar{D} caused per unit time can be estimated as:

$$\bar{D} = v_0^+ E\left(\frac{1}{N(s)}\right) \quad (4.3)$$

$$\bar{D} = v_0^+ \int_0^\infty \frac{p(s)}{N(s)} ds \quad (4.4)$$

where v_0^+ is the positive 0-level crossing rate and $p(s)$ is the stress amplitude probability density function. A more detailed derivation is given in Appendix C. $p(s)$ depends on the power spectral density of stress at the tower base S_{ss} , therefore the structure's motion needs to be related to internal stress. The model assumed linear torsional stiffness K_t at the base of the tower so that the bending moment at the tower base can be obtained from the relative displacement of the tower and the platform. Combined with Euler-Bernoulli beam theory, the maximum stress in the tower can be obtained as shown in equation 4.5.

$$s = \frac{(\theta_2 - \theta_1)K_t r_t}{I_t} \quad (4.5)$$

where r_t and I_t are respectively the radius and second moment of area at the tower base.

Assume θ_1 and θ_2 are RAOs (for a unit amplitude forcing) obtained as shown in section 3.4. s is then the RAO of the stress at the tower base. The RAO from unit amplitude waves is called s_1 and the RAO from unit amplitude wind turbulence is called s_2 . Ultimately the stress at the base is still dependent on the relative motion of the tower and the platform. The s_1 RAO for waves only is shown below.

Fig. 4.2 Base stress RAO for unit amplitude wave forces

As expected, Figure 4.2 is a linear amplification of Figure 3.23, which shows the variation of tower-platform angle difference with frequency. It is interesting to note that the peaks in Figure 4.2 do not always match with the platform pitch or tower pitch RAO peaks. For example, the peak caused by diffraction waves seems to be around 0.13Hz in Figure 4.2 while it is around 0.1Hz for the platform pitch alone. The target frequencies for the tuned mass dampers will consequently be different from the cases where the platform and the tower motions are reduced separately. This shows the importance of considering the system as a whole to reduce the dynamic response of the structure.

A correction should also be added to include the effect of constant gravity loading and mean wind thrust on the tower base stress. The Goodman relation applies a factor to the alternating stress amplitude σ_a with mean stress σ_m to find the equivalent stress amplitude for fully reversed loading σ_{rev} .

$$\sigma_{rev} = \sigma_a \frac{1}{1 - \frac{\sigma_m}{\sigma_{ult}}} \quad (4.6)$$

σ_{ult} is the ultimate tensile stress of steel and is given a value of 550 N/mm^2 [36]. The Goodman factor is dependent on the constant wind velocity but varies around 1.1.

The overall stress power spectral density is then obtained by combining the effects of wave and wind forcing:

$$S_{ss} = |s_1|^2 * S_{\eta\eta} + |s_2|^2 * S_{ww} \quad (4.7)$$

Once the power spectral density of tower base stress is obtained, σ_s is derived from equation 3.9 and equation 4.4 can be further expanded (see Appendix C) to yield the following result [50]:

$$\bar{D} = v_0 C^{-1} \left(\sqrt{2} \sigma_s \right)^k \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{k}{2}\right) \quad (4.8)$$

Equation 4.8 applies to narrow-banded signals. The Tovo-Benasciutti method (see Appendix C), which takes into account the spread of the process, adds a factor γ_{TB} to equation 4.8 [50]. The lifetime of a component is then obtained as:

$$T = \frac{1}{\bar{D}_{TB}} = \frac{1}{\gamma_{TB} * \bar{D}} \quad (4.9)$$

A final parameter which is commonly used in the literature to assess the fatigue improvement of a specific TMD configuration is the damage equivalent load (DEL). This corresponds to the stress amplitude of a constant amplitude harmonic load causing the same damage as the variable amplitude load for a given amount of cycles.

$$\frac{N_{eq}}{C s_{const}^{-k}} = \bar{D} \quad (4.10)$$

The constant amplitude stress (DEL) is therefore found as:

$$s_{const} = DEL = \left(\frac{N_{eq}}{\bar{D} C} \right)^{-\frac{1}{k}} \quad (4.11)$$

The DEL relative improvement between the base case and the configuration with TMDs can be expressed as follows:

$$\gamma_{DEL} = \frac{DEL_{base} - DEL_{TMD}}{DEL_{base}} \quad (4.12)$$

Using Equation 4.11, this can be derived into:

$$\gamma_{DEL} = \frac{\bar{D}_{base}^{\frac{1}{k}} - \bar{D}_{TMD}^{\frac{1}{k}}}{\bar{D}_{base}^{\frac{1}{k}}} \quad (4.13)$$

Note that this ratio is independent of N_{eq} and C . This is beneficial as the C coefficient represents a big source of uncertainty in determining the fatigue lifetime. γ_{DEL} will therefore be used to compare results of the model with results in the literature.

4.2 Local weather conditions

Section 4.1.2 shows that the fatigue damage on a component at a given time depends on the applied JONSWAP and Kaimal spectra. These are dependent on the environmental conditions on site, which vary considerably throughout the lifetime of the FOWT and as a function of the wind farm's location.

A study by [26] uses a hindcast model called NEXT to simulate environmental conditions at various locations in the North Sea, Irish Sea, Celtic Sea and the Channel, using wind and wave data obtained from 1977 to 1979 and 1989 to 1994. The grid points are shown below and those chosen for this study are marked with a red cross.

Fig. 4.3 Location of NEXT dataset points (map taken from [26])

The two points were chosen to be far apart with different geographic conditions to assess the influence of local weather conditions on the optimisation output. The fetch distances is one clear variable which can make results differ as the Celtic Sea is on the edge of the Atlantic Ocean while the Northern North Sea is more sheltered between the UK and Norway.

Each point is subjected to 78843 simulations calibrated to measured datasets. The wind and wave statistical properties at each site are derived from these simulations. Wave heights H_s , wave peak periods T_p and wind speeds at 10m above sea level $U_{wind_{10}}$ are grouped into bins as shown in Figures 4.4 and 4.5. The probability of each combination is obtained by counting the number of simulations falling into these bins and dividing by the total number of simulations.

Fig. 4.4 Wind speed-wave height correlation at two different sites (based on data taken from [26])

Fig. 4.5 Peak period-wave height correlation at two different sites (based on data taken from [26])

In Figure 4.4, the majority of the relevant environmental conditions are distributed along a relatively narrow band, implying that there is a strong positive correlation between local wind speed and significant wave height. If a direct relationship is established between H_s and $U_{wind_{10}}$, this allows to simplify the problem as the external forces will only depend on two rather than three random variables.

An exponential regression method is chosen to establish a relationship between $U_{wind_{10}}$ and H_s as it gives the highest R^2 values. For each H_s value in Figure 4.4, the wind speed with the highest probability of occurrence is taken as a data point for the regression curve, as shown in Figure 4.6.

(a) Exponential regression curve for U-Hs in North Sea

(b) Exponential regression curve for U-Hs in Celtic Sea

Fig. 4.6 Regression curves for U-Hs

The relationship between H_s and U given by Figure 4.6 is as follows:

$$H_s(U) = ae^{bU} \quad (4.14)$$

Since Figure 4.5 shows the correlation between H_s and T_p , it is more adequate to keep these two variables as independent and express U as a function of H_s :

$$U(H_s) = c * \log(DH_s) \quad (4.15)$$

The results are presented in Table 4.2

Table 4.2 Regression results for U-Hs relationship

Regression coefficients	North Sea	Celtic Sea
c	7.55	6.59
D	2.07	1.97

From these values the relationship between wind speed and wave height doesn't seem to differ too much for different locations, although in the Celtic Sea the same wave heights are reached at slightly lower wind speeds. Note that this correlation between wind and wave height supports the assumption of aligned wind and wave loads made at the beginning of Chapter 3

Once the equation for U as a function of H_s has been established, a factor needs to be applied to account for vertical wind shear causing variation of wind speeds with height, since the given wind speeds only apply at 10m height. Wind turbulence and rotor thrust are based on wind speeds at hub heights, which in this case is 90m above SWL. The power law is used to convert 10m height wind speed values to 90m values:

$$U_{90} = U_{10} \left(\frac{90}{10} \right)^\alpha \quad (4.16)$$

where the exponent α reflects atmospheric stability and surface roughness. For offshore conditions, a value of 0.11 is reasonable [34]. This implies that wind speeds at hub height are 1.27 higher than at 10m elevation.

When considering Figure 4.5, the distribution of peak period and wave height combinations seems more scattered, preventing any direct correlation to be established. The peak periods in the Celtic Sea also seem to be greater than in the North Sea for a given wave height. This could be related to the different fetch distances of these two locations.

To assess the overall lifetime of the structure under these different sea states, the model set up in Chapter 3 is run for each environmental condition. The fatigue lifetime obtained in each case is multiplied by the probability of occurrence of the corresponding sea state. The results are then summed up to obtain a fatigue lifetime $T_{fatigue}$ taking into account the probabilistic distribution of sea states.

$$T_{fatigue} = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m T(H_s(i), T_p(j)) * Prob(H_s(i), T_p(j)) \quad (4.17)$$

4.3 Optimisation approach

A model of the basic 3-DOF FOWT has been set up in the frequency domain and a procedure has been put in place to derive the fatigue damage over the FOWT's lifetime based on the output of the dynamic analysis. TMDs are now added to the model to reduce the fatigue damage on the structure.

4.3.1 Equation of motion of TMDs

Each TMD adds a new DOF to the floating turbine MDOF. The relative displacement between the floating structure and TMD_i is called x_{3+i} so that the relative displacement of TMD_1 is x_4 . The TMDs are restricted to uniaxial motion in the fore-aft direction but can be placed at any height along the tower or platform. In the tower, the TMDs are placed along the central axis while in the platform there is the possibility to place them either in the central cylinder under the tower or to evenly distribute them among the three offset cylinders, avoiding any static pitch from mass imbalances.

Separate equations of motion are set up for TMDs in the tower and the platform as in the latter the tower doesn't influence the TMD's motion. Lagrange's equation based on the energy principle is used again to derive the equations of motion of the TMDs.

TMD in the platform

The initial position of the TMD in the platform is expressed in cylindrical coordinates (r_p, θ_p) with respect to P as shown in Figure 4.7.

The kinetic and potential energies are derived with respect to point P. However P is not an inertial reference point. Following d'Alembert's principle of inertial forces, the translational inertia force on the TMD caused by pitch of the platform about the static metacentre and the surge motion of the platform must therefore be added to the equation of motion.

The platform also offers the possibility to off-centre the TMDs by placing them in each of the three offset cylinders, which is illustrated in Figure 4.7. In this case, the vertical component of inertial forces should also be taken into account.

Fig. 4.7 Coordinate system with offset TMDs

Representing the distance from the TMD to the metacentre by r_M , we obtain the following kinetic energy of the TMD:

$$T_x = \frac{1}{2} m_{TMD} \left(\dot{x}_1 + r_M \sin(\theta_p + \theta_1) + \dot{x}_4 \right)^2 \quad (4.18)$$

$$T_y = \frac{1}{2} m_{TMD} \left(r_M \cos(\theta_p + \theta_1) + \dot{x}_4 \tan \theta_1 \right)^2 \quad (4.19)$$

Note that only \dot{x}_4 corresponds to an inertial force with respect to P, the other components of the equation are inertial components with respect to the inertial reference frame. The last term in equation 4.19 corresponds to the vertical velocity as the TMD spring extends at an angle θ_1 .

The derivation of the inertia matrices obtained from equations 4.18 and 4.19 (see Appendix A.0.2) shows that using offset cylinders with the additional parameter T_y effectively increases the pitch moment of inertia of the platform and has the same impact as using central-axis TMDs with higher mass ratios. Off-setting the TMDs in the platform is thus more efficient and is done for the rest of the study. A TMD in the platform therefore consists in reality of three separate TMDs with the same properties equally distributed amongst the three offset cylinders.

The potential energy consists of the stiffness of the TMD spring and the gravity forces acting on the mass:

$$V = \frac{1}{2}K_{TMD}x_4^2 + m_{TMD}g r_p \cos(\theta_p + \theta_1) - m_{TMD}g x_4 \tan\theta_1 \quad (4.20)$$

The second term in Equation 4.20 corresponds to the change in height (and therefore potential energy) of the TMD as the platform rotates about P. The last term in Equation 4.20 corresponds to the change in height as the spring of the TMD extends at an angle θ_1 determined by the platform pitch, as shown in Figure 4.7.

The damping contribution of the TMD only depends on its own damper:

$$W_{TMD} = \frac{1}{2}D_{TMD}\dot{x}_4^2 \quad (4.21)$$

Equations 4.18 to 4.21 are then differentiated with respect to each DOF and simplified assuming small angular displacement and velocity approximation (see Appendix A). Note that the kinetic energy equation needs to be differentiated again with respect to time to obtain inertia forces. The resulting matrices can be added to M , K and C obtained in the base case.

TMD in tower

For TMDs installed in the tower, the DOF θ_2 corresponding to the tower displacement affects the TMD motion as well. On the other hand, θ_p is always 0, which simplifies the equations. The kinetic energy is obtained as:

$$T = \frac{1}{2}m_{TMD} \left(\dot{x}_1 + r_{M_t} \sin\theta_1 + r_{TMD} \sin\theta_2 + \dot{x}_4 \right)^2 \quad (4.22)$$

where r_{M_t} is the distance between the metacentre and the tower base; r_{TMD} is the distance between the tower base and the TMD.

The potential energy function is:

$$V = \frac{1}{2}K_{TMD}x_4^2 + mg \left(H_c \cos\theta_1 + r_{TMD} \cos\theta_2 \right) - mg x_4 \tan\theta_2 \quad (4.23)$$

The work done by the dampers is:

$$W_{TMD} = \frac{1}{2}D_{TMD}\dot{x}_4^2 \quad (4.24)$$

Again, each of these functions must be differentiated with respect to each DOF to obtain the matrices to add to the base case EOM.

4.3.2 Target frequency

Once the TMDs are included in the equation of motion, their parameters have to be optimised to maximise their impact on vibration reductions of the FOWT. The angle difference at the base of the tower (and therefore the stress at this location) varies a lot with frequency, as made clear by Figure 3.23. Therefore different environmental conditions, acting at different frequencies with different probabilities, create a varying contribution to fatigue damage from each frequency.

To assess the overall fatigue damage over a structure's lifetime as a function of frequency, the peaks of the stress response in the frequency domain are first sampled for each environmental condition. The fatigue damage caused by each of these peaks separately is calculated using the method developed in section 4.1.2, with the stress distribution at frequencies outside of the peak range set to zero. The fatigue damage $\bar{D}(s)$ of each peak is then multiplied by the probability of occurrence $P(H_s, T_p)$ of the corresponding environmental condition throughout the lifetime of the FOWT. This gives an idea of the frequencies at which stress peaks occur the most and how damaging these peaks are. The results over all the sampled environmental conditions in the North North Sea are shown in Figure 4.8.

Fig. 4.8 Frequency distribution of fatigue damage for North North Sea conditions

Note that for the same stress amplitude, higher frequencies cause more damage due to the logarithmic shape of the S-N fatigue curves. Three main frequency domains contributing to fatigue are deduced from Figure 4.8. At very low frequencies, there is a clear peak coinciding with the surge

natural frequency of the FOWT, which is excited by the low-frequency Kaimal turbulence spectrum. At high frequencies, the natural frequency of the tower is excited by wave spectra with high frequency content, which corresponds to calmer sea states with lower wave heights. The last and most interesting fatigue damage contribution is between 0.08Hz and 0.17Hz. This corresponds to the wave frequency range with the highest probability of occurrence and coincides with the pitch RAO peak caused by diffraction forces, as identified in section 3.2.3. This peak extends over a wider range of frequencies, capturing different wave states. Considering the logarithmic scale of Figure 4.8, it is by far the most damaging frequency range. TMD tuning should therefore focus on this frequency range.

4.3.3 Issues at low frequency

Low-frequency TMDs require low stiffness springs relative to their mass. This implies large motion amplitudes, which quickly become unrealistic if the physical boundary conditions of the tower and platform walls are not added to the model. In fact, for too low TMD spring stiffness values the overall stiffness matrix \mathbf{K} has eigenvalues numerically close to 0, which means it is not positive definite anymore. Yet a positive definite stiffness matrix is one of the requirements for a stable structure to have positive natural frequencies [28]. Hence heavy TMDs with low stiffness can cause such inconsistencies, which implies that the system is undergoing an unstable mechanism. The mass m_{TMD} and stiffness K_{TMD} of the TMD should therefore be constrained to a limited range yielding physically possible results.

In general, if physical boundaries were added to the model this would create non-linearities which are difficult to model in the frequency domain. In [45], where a TMD is installed at the top of the nacelle of a turbine installed on a semi-submersible, results of TMD parameters optimised around 0.02Hz show that these low-frequency TMDs heavily interact with the nacelle walls.

In view of the modelling complications brought by low-frequency TMDs and the fact that low-frequency vibrations only contribute a minor part to fatigue damage, as shown in section 4.3.2, it is decided to focus the optimisation of TMD parameters on higher frequency ranges. As wind turbulence mainly acts in the low frequency range, it will not be considered for the TMD parameter optimisation choices but is still included in the model to reproduce the overall dynamics of the structure. In general, wind turbulence seems important for displacement behaviour but less so for fatigue.

Chapter 5

Results and discussion

5.1 Baseline scenario

The baseline scenario has no TMDs installed and represents the fatigue lifetime of the turbine subjected to wind and wave loading according to their respective probability distribution at a specific site. Results are shown at the two sites around the British Isles considered previously, along with results from a data point in the more sheltered Irish Sea for comparative purposes.

Table 5.1 Baseline scenario

	North North Sea	Celtic Sea	Irish Sea
Fatigue life	30.2 years	37.6 years	231 years

The fatigue lifetime in the North Sea corresponds approximately to the target lifetime of offshore wind turbines. However, as mentioned previously, this value could vary significantly if only slightly different values were taken, which makes fatigue reduction still a major concern. Conditions in the Celtic Sea seem to be less harsh but not safe enough to be ignored. On the other hand, fatigue doesn't seem to be a problem in the Irish Sea. Due to its geographic location, the Irish Sea is sheltered from large fetch distances, which only allows small wave heights to develop. Only the two first locations will therefore be considered for the rest of this analysis.

The frequency distribution of fatigue damage peaks for the Celtic Sea shows a very similar behaviour to the one shown for North North Sea in Figure 4.8, with a clear peak around the diffraction-dominated frequency range. The TMD optimisation process developed below for North North Sea conditions should therefore also be applicable to floating structures in the Celtic Sea.

5.2 Setting up

5.2.1 Tower-platform connection

Ultimately, the fatigue behaviour at the tower base depends on the platform pitch θ_1 and the tower pitch θ_2 . From the frequency domain analysis, θ_1 and θ_2 are obtained as imaginary numbers and can therefore be expressed as a function of magnitude and phase. A difference in either magnitude or phase between the platform and tower angles will be detrimental. The angle difference plot shown in Figure 5.1a for the baseline scenario in the North Sea is derived as $\Delta\theta = |\theta_2 - \theta_1|$. This allows to take the magnitude and phase difference simultaneously into account. The phase difference between the two angles is also shown in Figure 5.1b:

(a) Tower base absolute angle difference $|\theta_2 - \theta_1|$

(b) Tower base angle phase difference $\alpha_{\theta_2} - \alpha_{\theta_1}$

Fig. 5.1 Tower-platform angle difference for baseline scenario

In Figure 5.1a, neglecting the peak at low frequency corresponding to the surge natural frequency, the maximum angle difference occurs between 0.1 and 0.2 Hz, at the diffraction excitation frequency.

Apart from a few more harmonics from diffraction forces, another peak occurs near 0.4Hz which corresponds to the tower's natural frequency.

In Figure 5.1b, the phase difference seems to increase with frequency. As the value is negative, this means that the platform's vibrations are leading the tower's vibrations. This explains why the high-frequency peaks in 5.1a are relatively high while motion magnitudes in this range are small. Bodies moving out of phase will create very large angle differences despite small motions, which generates stress at the connection.

Focusing the TMD action between 0.1Hz and 0.2Hz allows to target an area with both significant magnitude difference and non-negligible phase difference.

Before results are analysed, it is important to discuss the constant spring stiffness chosen to model the tower-platform connection. As it governs the relative motion of the two bodies, results will be very sensitive to the calibration of this value. In this study a value of $1.594 \cdot 10^{10} N/m$ was taken from [45], which also models a rigid turbine connected to a semi submersible base using a linear spring calibrated against fully coupled FAST outputs.

A comparison is made between [45] results and this research's dynamic model for the following TMD parameter values given in [45]:

- Position: turbine nacelle (80m above platform)
- Mass TMD: 20 000kg
- Damping: 9000 N/(m/s)
- Natural frequency of TMD: 0.4Hz
- Operational condition: at rated wind speed (10m/s) in [45]; following probability distribution in model

The results compare the DEL ratio improvement for tower base stress. A third column is added to represent the dynamic model results if a stiffer connection of $2.5 \cdot 10^{10} N/m$ were to be chosen in the model.

Table 5.2 Results comparison with [45]

	Result from [45]	$K = 1.594 \cdot 10^{10} N/m$ result	$K = 2.5 \cdot 10^{10} N/m$ result
DEL reduction	7.78%	-6.05%	7.43%
Displacement reduction	-1.55%	0.4%	-0.9%

In terms of DEL ratio improvement, the current model seems to behave in an opposite way to what [45] predicts. This could be due to a miscalibrated tower connection. The stiffer the

connection, the closer the tower motion will be to that of the platform. Motion reduction in the tower will then lead to motion reduction in the platform. However for a 'softer' connection, the two bodies move more independently so that a motion reduction in the tower could lead to an increased differential motion between the tower and the platform.

Fig. 5.2 Effect of different connection stiffness on fatigue and displacement behaviour

Figure 5.2 shows that changing the stiffness of the tower-platform connection one way or another is either beneficial for reducing displacements or fatigue. Whether stiffness modifications improve displacement or fatigue behaviour will depend on the initial angle phase and magnitude difference at a certain frequency. The displacements displayed in Table 5.2 confirm that displacement reduction has opposite requirements to fatigue reduction. The average tower top displacement can be expressed as follows:

$$\sigma_{TTD} = \sigma_{(x_1 + \theta_1 * H_c + \theta_2 * R_{hub})} \quad (5.1)$$

In this case, increasing the phase difference between θ_1 and θ_2 is beneficial. Lastly, higher connection stiffnesses can decrease motion amplitudes at the cost of increased load cycles, which can be detrimental for fatigue loading.

This sensitivity of the model to the connection stiffness is a major drawback. However it underlines the importance of this structural component in the dynamics of FOWTs. The stiffness of this connection could in the future be designed in a state of Pareto optimality between displacement and fatigue depending on design priorities. The 'soft' connection value of $1.594 \times 10^10 \text{N/m}$ will be kept for the rest of this analysis.

5.3 Optimisation with single tuned mass damper

The parameters of interest for a single tuned mass damper are:

- Mass
- Spring stiffness and consequently natural frequency of TMD
- Damping coefficient of damper
- Position within structure

The NNS case will be used here as the example case. A first analysis is made focusing the TMD frequency on 0.15Hz, as concluded from section 4.3.2.

The fatigue analysis is iterated over a range of position, mass and damping values. The spring stiffness is adjusted to the mass to meet the target natural frequency of 0.15Hz. The mass ratio range follows the recommendations given by [63], spanning between 0.5% and 4% of the structure's total mass. Note that the mass ratios in the tower should be relative to the tower mass only, in which case 4% of the tower mass is 24 000kg. A separate analysis must therefore be done on the tower .

5.3.1 TMD in the platform

The following values are used in the platform:

- TMD position in platform: [-25, -15, -5, -3, -1]m. The tower-platform connection is used as the reference point so that negative values are in the platform and positive values are in the tower.
- TMD mass in platform: 11 points evenly distributed between 48 000kg and 560 000kg, which corresponds to mass ratios between 0.3% and 4% of the total FOWT mass.
- TMD damping in platform: [10 000, 30 000, 60 000, 120 000, 180 000, 240 000] N/(m/s)

Results are expressed as DEL reduction ratios γ_{DEL} , as defined in section 4.1.2, with positive values indicating a reduction in equivalent stress amplitudes.

Figure 5.3 shows the effect of varying the TMD mass, the TMD position and the TMD damper value D when keeping the TMD in the platform.

Fig. 5.3 DEL improvements as a function of mass and position at different damping coefficients D of a STMD in the platform

Apart from the heaviest masses at low damping, it seems that TMDs placed in the platform reduce the equivalent stress amplitude at the tower connection and thus improve the fatigue behaviour of the structure. Amongst the tested values, the highest achieved DEL improvement ratio is 0.0612. It seems that for all four damping values the maximum DEL improvement is achieved when the TMD is placed at -1m, just under the platform-tower connection. This is true provided that the mass is adequately adjusted to the damping value. The model also indicates on the other hand that average tower top displacement is minimised for a TMD placed at -25m, which corresponds to the bottom of the platform. Again, contradictory results arise depending on the desired outcome. The mass at which maximum DEL improvement is reached varies with the chosen damping value. As the damper is the source of energy extraction in the device, it must be configured to maximise the work it can do. The work done by the damper depends on the damping coefficient and the relative velocity of the damper with respect to the structure. If the damping coefficient is too high compared to the TMD mass, the relative motion of the TMD will be negligible and little work is generated. In this case the TMD is essentially locked to the structures motion and simply acts like

an extra mass. This corresponds to the situation to the left of the peaks observed in Figure 5.3 at $D=10\,000\text{ N/(m/s)}$. If the damping coefficient is too low relative to the TMD's mass, the TMD's inertial force will prevent large motions and again the relative motion of the TMD with the main structure is suboptimal. This corresponds to the masses to the right of the peak.

For higher damping values, where the mass corresponding to the optimal peak is outside the mass range considered, the DEL improvement invariably increases with mass. As damping increases, the TMD becomes more and more locked-in to the structure and yet the DEL ratio seems to improve even further, as is shown in Figure 5.4.

Fig. 5.4 DEL improvement for STMD in platform at different damping values D , positions R and mass m

This is because at high damping values the TMD is essentially part of the structure and increases its inertial mass, consequently reducing the response of the structure to external forces even though the damper doesn't do much work. The question arises whether a mass simply attached to the structure would do just as well. The experiment was therefore repeated including very high damping values to mimic a locked-in mass. The position of the TMD was fixed at -1m .

Fig. 5.5 Effect of very high damping coefficients on DEL improvement ratio

Figure 5.5 shows that keeping the mass completely fixed to the structure does not achieve optimal results and some motion of the TMD has to be allowed to extract energy. A balance has to be found between improving the inertial properties of the main structure and letting the TMD damper extract some energy. Since a heavier TMD will have more influence on the structure, a high mass-high damping TMD configuration is preferred.

The impact of the most effective STMD (450 000kg with 120 000 N/(m/s) damping positioned 1m under the tower connection) on the structure's dynamics is shown in the following figures.

Fig. 5.6 Wave-excited RAOs of each DOF with added TMD

At 0.15Hz, the TMD doesn't interact with the natural frequencies of the original structure. A clear displacement peak is however shown at the TMD resonant frequency, which shows the damper is exerting some work. The impact of this work can be seen by analysing the change in angle difference between the tower and the platform.

(a) Impact of TMD on $|\theta_2 - \theta_1|$

(b) Impact of TMD on $\alpha_{\theta_2} - \alpha_{\theta_1}$

Fig. 5.7 Tower-platform angle difference with optimal single TMD

The peak value is clearly decreased which is characteristic of a damper acting on the system. The original peak is split into two slightly offset peaks, which shows the frequency shifting achieved by the TMD. The improvements near 0.15Hz are slightly offset by angle difference increases on either side of the peak, but these don't contribute as much to fatigue. The angle phase difference shows that the TMD not only decreases the magnitude of the angle difference but also the phase. The final impact on the tower base stress is exemplified by the power spectral density shown in Figure 5.8 for an example sea state ($H_s = 3m, T_p = 8s$).

Fig. 5.8 Tower base stress PSD for optimal STMD at 0.15Hz

Damping optimisation according to Den Hartog

As mentioned in section 2.3.1, Den Hartog established a relationship between TMD mass and optimal damping for a SDOF system [19]:

$$D_{TMD} = 2 * m_{TMD} * \omega_{target} * \sqrt{\frac{3\mu}{8(1+\mu)^3}} \quad (5.2)$$

In this case ω_{target} corresponds to the frequency at peak diffraction forces. For a TMD positioned at -1m, which was established to be the most effective position, a range of masses are tested at different constant damping values and additionally with Den Hartog's adaptive damping value to see if it yields any improvements.

Fig. 5.9 Comparison of results between Den Hartog's damping and constant damping values

The results in Figure 5.9 clearly show that Den Hartog's damping value adapts to the mass to yield the maximum DEL ratio improvement for each mass. Den Hartog's relation is therefore kept for the rest of the analysis.

5.3.2 TMD in the tower

The values used in the tower are:

- TMD position in tower: [5,15,25,45,80]m
- TMD mass in tower: [5 000,8 000,12 000,16 000,20 000]kg
- TMD damping in tower: [1 000, 2 000, 5 000, 10 000, 30 000, 50 000, 80 000, 120 000] N/(m/s)

Example results are displayed for two different damping values in Figure 5.10.

Fig. 5.10 DEL improvement for STMD in tower

Clearly the impact of the TMDs in the tower is negative. In fact, this applies for the whole range of damping values tested, over all mass and position values. While in the platform the weight of the TMD acts as a restoring force, gravity acting on elements in the tower is a destabilising force, therefore the higher the element the worse the stress at the tower base.

However, in [45] some TMDs are installed in the nacelle with successful results when tuned to higher frequencies around 0.4Hz. Using similar target frequencies in this model results in negative DEL improvement ratios but positive displacement reductions. It is believed that in [45] the tower connection stiffness is comparatively higher, which means that the displacement reductions in the tower affect the platform displacement to a higher extent than in this model. As the tower's natural frequency is around 0.4Hz, a TMD tuned at 0.4Hz will be effective in reducing overall displacements in the case of a stiff connection, whereas it will only decrease tower motions for a more flexible connection, in which case fatigue damage is increased.

From the parameters used in this analysis, a TMD placed in the tower is detrimental for fatigue reduction. For this reason TMDs will not be used in the tower for the rest of the analysis.

5.3.3 TMDs at different frequencies

The analysis for a single TMD concluded so far that the TMD should be positioned in the platform at -1m, with the highest allowable mass ratios and a corresponding damping set by Den Hartog's relationship. In this case, a DEL improvement ratio of 6.12% is achieved. However, this only applies for the case where the natural frequency of the TMD is tuned to 0.15Hz.

New simulations are done for a range of target frequencies spanning between 0.07Hz and 0.23Hz, which is the frequency area identified as critical for the fatigue lifetime. The tested TMD masses are [75000,150000,350000,450000]kg, with corresponding Den Hartog damping values. The different TMD positions tested are [-25,-15,-8,-1]m. At each target frequency and each TMD position, heavier TMD masses turn out to be the most effective again. The best performance cases for each target frequency and position configuration are displayed in Figure 5.11.

Fig. 5.11 Frequency dependence of STMD

At all positions in general, the optimal TMD tuning frequency seems to be either side of the peak damage frequency identified in Figure 4.8. This is because the TMD frequency has to be near enough to the peak value to get a response from the damper but far enough from it to avoid excessive resonance of the TMD which would increase vibrations in the structure as a whole.

The TMD position at -1m seems to be the optimal solution at almost every frequency, so that it is taken as the optimal value for the rest of the analysis. For a TMD placed at -1m, the optimal frequency is 0.17Hz, at which point a DEL improvement ratio of 6.68% is reached. This corresponds to a fatigue lifetime improvement of 23.0% from 30.2 years to 37.14 years. The optimal configuration focuses on the higher end of the diffraction peak frequency range as it undergoes

more cycles in the turbine's lifetime and is therefore more detrimental to fatigue.

Considering these results take into account the whole range of weather conditions affecting the turbine, they can be considered an improvement on the figures quoted from the literature in section 2.3.3, where the DEL improvement ratio for the semi-submersible in [45] varied between 0.18% and 7.78% depending on the weather condition considered.

The final optimal properties for a single TMD applied to the semi submersible FOWT are summarised below:

- Position: Evenly distributed in offset cylinders of platform, 1m below tower connection.
- Mass: 450 000kg (sum of distributed masses)
- Damping: 120 000 N/(m/s) (corresponds to Den Hartog's optimal)
- Target frequency (determines spring stiffness given the mass): 0.17Hz

5.4 Effect of multiple tuned mass dampers

So far the use of a TMD has been effective to reduce the stress response peak around 0.13Hz. Could multiple masses acting over a broader frequency range spread their damping effect over a wider response range and therefore be more effective?

The sum of the MTMD masses is set to be equal to the mass of the single TMD they are compared to. The optimal (and maximum) STMD value of 450 000kg is taken for this purpose. The damping of each individual TMD is set based on Den Hartog's optimal damping value. The position is once again fixed at -1m. The variables that remain to be determined are the optimal number of TMDs, the target tuning frequency of each TMD and the mass distribution amongst all TMDs.

5.4.1 Number of TMDs

A first analysis is done with the mass equally distributed between the TMDs. Each TMD is tuned to a specific frequency with a constant interval between each TMD's natural frequency. The frequency range covered is centered about a specified frequency focus point. The following MTMD configurations are tested:

- Number of TMDs: [1,2,3,4,9,10]
- Frequency focus of the TMDs: [0.11,0.13,0.15,0.17,0.19] Hz
- Frequency interval between TMDs: [0.05,0.1,0.15]Hz

The results are shown in Figure 5.12 for the three frequency intervals considered:

Fig. 5.12 Results for uniformly distributed MTMDs

Figure 5.12a shows that too closely spaced damper frequencies are not effective and that many TMDs are required to cover a broad enough frequency range to make a difference. Nonetheless, MTMDs show better results than the single TMD. In figure 5.12b, the frequency range covered is broad enough to effectively dampen out a considerable part of the wave frequencies. The function corresponding to 10 TMDs shows that if the masses are too thinly spread across a wide range of frequencies the most detrimental frequencies are not damped out enough and the MTMD configuration is not as effective. This is exacerbated in Figure 5.12c where the MTMD configurations which are too spread out (with a high number of TMDs) need to shift their focus frequency to 0.15Hz to have enough dampers in the critical frequency range around 0.17Hz. In this figure it is also seen that a configuration with 4 TMDs with wider frequency intervals can be as effective as 9 or 10 TMDs with more closely spaced frequencies. Therefore 4 TMDs will be used for the MTMD configuration

as it allows to cover a large enough frequency band while staying relatively economical in cost and complexity.

5.4.2 Frequency and mass distribution

The results obtained so far indicate that optimal TMD configurations concentrate on the upper frequency end of the peak between 0.1Hz and 0.2Hz. This is due to the higher fatigue impact of loads with higher cycles. This suggests an asymmetric behaviour around the focus frequencies chosen so far. Therefore the last analysis made for MTMDs considers varying configurations of mass and frequency distributions, including asymmetric ones, for the 4-TMD setup chosen.

The different frequency distributions around the focus frequency are shown in Figure 5.13.

Fig. 5.13 Different frequency configurations tested for MTMD

Note that F1 corresponds to the case where all TMDs are set to the focus frequency. F2, F3 and F4 are all uniformly and symmetrically distributed about f_{focus} but at different frequency intervals Δf of 0.05Hz, 0.1Hz and 0.2Hz. Configurations F5 to F8 allow to assess the importance of TMDs close to the focus frequency versus more dispersed TMDs.

Similarly, different TMD mass configurations are chosen, as displayed in Figure 5.14. Note that the size of each TMD in the diagram is only relative to the other ones in the same configuration. The total mass of each configuration is always equal to 450 000kg.

Fig. 5.14 Different mass configurations tested for MTMD

M1 puts more emphasis on frequencies closer to the focus frequency. Conversely M3 puts more emphasis on frequencies further away. Asymmetric mass configurations M4 and M5 allow to put more emphasis on respectively lower and higher frequencies.

Combining these different configurations of mass and frequency allows to obtain the optimal MTMD configuration out of 40 different setups. The best results are obtained with a focus frequency of 0.165Hz and are shown in Figure 5.15.

Fig. 5.15 MTMD configuration results

The DEL improvement (reduction) ratio appears to be more sensitive to frequency configuration than mass configuration. Within the frequency configurations, it seems that F4, F7 and F8, which all contain TMDs at frequencies further away from the focus frequency, are not as effective. F1 and F2, which have TMD frequencies close to the focus frequency, have a relatively low performance as well. The maximum DEL improvement ratio is 6.86%, which corresponds to a 23.7% increase in fatigue lifetime from 30.2 years to 37.4 years. This optimal result is obtained at the configuration (F3, M3) which represents a uniform frequency distribution with slightly more weight put on the frequencies further away from the focus frequency.

In general the results between the different configurations do not differ much, as long as the TMDs' natural frequencies are not too close or too far from 0.17Hz. This makes MTMDs more resilient to damper de-tuning compared to STMD. However when comparing the outputs of the optimal MTMD configuration with the output of the optimal STMD configuration, it appears that MTMDs only improve the DEL ratio by 0.18% more, which means the fatigue lifetime increases by 23.7% instead of 23.0%. This difference is too small to show a clear advantage. It implies that for simplicity of construction, single tuned mass dampers are recommended to use in the OC4 semi submersible FOWT.

5.5 Recommendations for future work

The optimisation process done in the previous sections largely relies on an exhaustive method, where parameters are set to their optimal parameter value after evaluating their impact on the results over a range of values. Eventually each parameter is optimised and the best performing result is obtained. However, this method can neglect certain parameter configurations which are only optimal when combined with other parameters. More robust optimisation methods should be used to obtain a general optimal result. In previous papers on TMD optimisation such as [63], [64] and [3], the genetic algorithm is used to achieve this. The genetic algorithm is based on the Darwinian principle of the survival of the fittest, where an initial population undergoes a fitness test (in this case the fatigue behaviour) and only the best performing individuals are selected for the next generation. Random mutations and cross-overs allow to eventually converge to an optimal value after several generations. This method allows to explore unknown domains of interest and is very suited to highly non-linear optimisation methods where New-Raphson methods can only find local maxima [3].

To improve the model, certain parameters such as the tower base stiffness should be adequately calibrated against results from fully coupled time-domain simulations from established software such as FAST or Bladed. Additional efforts should also be put in the modelling of aerodynamic

forces in the frequency domain, for example taking into account wake turbulence caused by the operating turbine. Adding more degrees of freedom to the system, with the tower and the turbine blades as aeroelastic bodies instead of rigid bodies, would be a further step towards reaching more accurate values. Nonetheless, the modelling choices made in this study allowed to obtain accurate enough results to draw relevant conclusions on the use of TMDs in a semi-submersible floating turbine.

Finally, a complementary study to this project would be the optimisation of FOWT dynamics for tower top displacement minimisation. The objective function in this case could be the power output of the turbine, as the tower top motion will affect the aerodynamics of the turbine and therefore the power output of the generator. Since displacement and fatigue reduction were shown to have contradicting requirements, a Pareto optimality study should be done to determine the overall optimal TMD configuration to satisfy both criteria.

Chapter 6

Conclusion

This research project focuses on reducing fatigue loads over the lifetime of a semi-submersible wind turbine using tuned mass dampers. The analysis requires a fast yet accurate computation method to analyse a great number of different loading conditions and TMD configurations to eventually reach an optimal solution.

To answer this, the study consists of three main parts. First, a model is set up in the frequency domain, which has much lower computation times than the time domain but cannot handle non-linear phenomena. A floating wind turbine is subjected to interacting hydrodynamic, aerodynamic and structural loads, some being highly non-linear. While the results from the linearisation of hydrodynamic forces agree with the literature, linearisation of aerodynamic forces is only acceptable for operation in steady conditions. In order to model more realistic operation conditions including aerodynamic control, data obtained from time domain simulations done in the literature is used as input for the aerodynamic forces. This dependence on external data implies a loss of generality of the model as the results are only applicable to the turbine configurations tested in the literature.

An important conclusion of this first section is the existence of a response peak close to the typical ocean-wave frequency range, caused by the specific geometry of the semi-submersible. The relative pitch motion of the platform and tower is also shown to be very sensitive to the stiffness of the platform-tower connection. Depending on this value, either tower top displacement or fatigue loads are reduced. A connection stiffness value is taken from similar models in the literature but would need to be validated comparing results with fully coupled simulation software.

In a second part, fatigue damage is assessed at the tower base using the stress distribution in the frequency domain obtained from the dynamic model. The Damage Equivalent Load is used as the measured output to avoid the sensitivity of fatigue lifetime to input parameters. The fatigue damage caused by specific wave and wind conditions is weighted by the probability of occurrence of these

weather conditions, based on the statistical distribution of wind and wave amplitudes for a specific site. From this, it appears that the response peak in the ocean-wave frequency range identified in the first section is contributing the most to fatigue damage. This result seems valid irrespective of the site considered in Northern Europe.

The third part focuses on choosing TMD parameters which minimise the impact of the ocean-wave frequency peak. Parameters of interest are mass, damping coefficient, stiffness and position of the damper. A first parametric study is done on a single TMD before drawing overall conclusions using multiple TMDs. In general, TMDs in the tower are detrimental and the optimum configuration for a STMD is at the top of the platform, at maximum mass ratio with a damping coefficient adjusted based on Den Hartog's equation. The DEL value is thereby reduced by 6.7%, which corresponds to a 23% increase in the turbine's lifetime. Additional gains from using MTMDs are not high enough to be of interest.

The geometry of the semi-submersible is identified to be particularly prone to fatigue damage. The results in this report show that TMDs are an effective and feasible passive control system for fatigue reduction in semi-submersible wind turbines, but that better platform design choices could considerably reduce the fatigue problem in the first place. In general this study provides a methodology for assessing long-term loading on floating wind turbines. While floating wind turbine technology is still at the prototype stage, it is important to design this infrastructure taking long-term effects into consideration in order to build a reliable and sustainable power generation source for the future.

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Appendix A

Equation of motion from Lagrangian method

In the following derivations, the small angle approximation is made. This implies that $\sin\theta_1 \approx \theta_1$, $\sin\dot{\theta}_1 \approx \dot{\theta}_1$, $\cos\dot{\theta}_1 \approx 1$ and $\cos\theta_1 \approx 1$. As the motion amplitudes and frequencies considered for a FOWT are relatively low, this is a reasonable assumption.

A.0.1 Base scenario EOM without TMDs

(refer to section 3.4.1 for explanation of each term)

General inertia forces:

$$T = \frac{1}{2}(I_p + A_r)\dot{\theta}_1^2 + \frac{1}{2}I_t\dot{\theta}_2^2 + \frac{1}{2}m_t(x_1 + MC_t\sin\dot{\theta}_1)^2 + \frac{1}{2}(m_p + A_t)(x_1 + MC_p\sin\dot{\theta}_1)^2$$

A_t and A_r are the added mass terms for pure surge and pitch motions about the centre of mass. For the coordinate system chosen (at P), off-diagonal terms arise. The added mass matrix can then be obtained as:

- $A_{11} = A_t$
- $A_{12} = A_{21} = A_t * MC_p$
- $A_{22} = A_r + A_t MC_p^2$

The coupling term $A_t * MC_p$ is equal to A_{12} and A_{21} , as the matrix is symmetric.

Differentiating with respect to each DOF and with time:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{d}{dt}\left(\frac{dT}{dx_1}\right) &= (m_t + m_p + A_{11})\ddot{x}_1 + (m_t MC_t + m_p MC_p + A_{12})\ddot{\theta}_1 \\ \frac{d}{dt}\left(\frac{dT}{d\dot{\theta}_1}\right) &= (m_t MC_t + m_p MC_p + A_{21})\ddot{x}_1 + (I_p + A_{22} + m_t MC_t^2 + m_p MC_p^2)\ddot{\theta}_1 \\ \frac{d}{dt}\left(\frac{dT}{d\dot{\theta}_2}\right) &= I_t \ddot{\theta}_2\end{aligned}$$

$$M_b = \begin{bmatrix} m_t + m_p + A_{11} & m_t MC_t + m_p MC_p + A_{12} & 0 \\ m_t MC_t + m_p MC_p + A_{21} & I_p + A_{22} + m_t MC_t^2 + m_p MC_p^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & I_t \ddot{\theta}_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

General stiffness forces:

$$V = K_{moor}(x_1, \theta_1) + \frac{1}{2}K_{hstatic}\theta_1^2 + \frac{1}{2}K_{tower}(\theta_1 - \theta_2)^2 - m_p g \cos(\theta_1)R_p + m_t g (R_{tower} \cos(\theta_2) + H_c \cos(\theta_1)) \quad (A.1)$$

Differentiating with respect to each DOF:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dV}{dx_1} &= K_{11}x_1 + K_{12}\theta_1 \\ \frac{dV}{d\theta_1} &= K_{21}x_1 + K_{22}\theta_1 + K_{hstatic}\theta_1 + K_{tower}(\theta_1 - \theta_2) + m_p g \theta_1 R_p - m_t g H_c \theta_1 \\ \frac{dV}{d\theta_2} &= -K_{tower}(\theta_1 - \theta_2) - m_t g R_{tower} \theta_2\end{aligned}$$

The stiffness matrix can then be obtained as:

$$K_b = \begin{bmatrix} K_{11} & K_{12} & 0 \\ K_{21} & K_{22} + K_{hstatic} + K_{tower} + m_p g R_p - m_t g H_c & -K_{tower} \\ 0 & -K_{tower} & K_{tower} - m_t g R_{tower} \end{bmatrix}$$

The work W_D done by the damping forces is expressed as:

$$W_D = \frac{1}{2} D_{tower} (\dot{\theta}_1 - \dot{\theta}_2)^2 + D_{hydro} (\dot{x}_1, \dot{\theta}_1) + \frac{1}{2} D_{drift} \dot{x}_1^2 + \frac{1}{2} c_a (\dot{x}_1 + H_c \dot{\theta}_1 + R_{hub} \dot{\theta}_2)^2 \quad (A.2)$$

Differentiating with respect to each DOF:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dW_D}{dx_1} &= D_{11} \dot{x}_1 + D_{12} \dot{\theta}_1 + D_{drift} \dot{x}_1 + c_a (\dot{x}_1 + H_c \dot{\theta}_1 + R_{hub} \dot{\theta}_2) \\ \frac{dW_D}{d\theta_1} &= D_{tower} (\dot{\theta}_1 - \dot{\theta}_2) + D_{21} \dot{x}_1 + D_{22} \dot{\theta}_1 + H_c c_a (\dot{x}_1 + H_c \dot{\theta}_1 + R_{hub} \dot{\theta}_2) \\ \frac{dW_D}{d\theta_2} &= -D_{tower} (\dot{\theta}_1 - \dot{\theta}_2) + R_{hub} c_a (\dot{x}_1 + H_c \dot{\theta}_1 + R_{hub} \dot{\theta}_2) \end{aligned}$$

The damping matrix can then be obtained as:

$$D_b = \begin{bmatrix} D_{11} + D_{drift} + c_a & D_{12} + c_a H_c & c_a R_{hub} \\ D_{21} + H_c c_a & D_{tower} + D_{22} + H_c^2 c_a & -D_{tower} + H_c c_a R_{hub} \\ R_{hub} c_a & -D_{tower} + R_{hub} c_a H_c & D_{tower} + R_{hub}^2 c_a \end{bmatrix}$$

A.0.2 Contribution of tuned mass dampers to EOM

: The location of the TMD is governed by R_{TMD} , which represents the distance from the tower-platform connection to the TMD. TMDs in the platform have negative R_{TMD} values while TMDs in the tower have positive R_{TMD} values. If the TMD is located in the platform ($R_{TMD} < 0$), there is a possibility of placing the TMD in the three off-centered cylinders. The position of the TMD is therefore translated into cylindrical coordinates with respect to P as (r_p, θ_p) .

In the platform

Inertial force in the x-direction:

$$T_x = \frac{1}{2}m_{TMD} \left(\dot{x}_1 + r_M \sin(\theta_p + \theta_1) + \dot{x}_{TMD} \right)^2 \quad (\text{A.3})$$

Differentiating with respect to each DOF:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{dT_x}{dx_1} \right) &= m_{TMD} \left(\ddot{x}_1 + r_M \cos \theta_p \ddot{\theta}_1 + \ddot{x}_{TMD} \right) \\ \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{dT_x}{d\theta_1} \right) &= m_{TMD} r_M \cos \theta_p \left(\ddot{x}_1 + r_M \cos(\theta_p) \ddot{\theta}_1 + \ddot{x}_{TMD} \right) \\ \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{dT_x}{d\theta_2} \right) &= 0 \\ \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{dT_x}{dx_{TMD}} \right) &= m_{TMD} \left(\dot{x}_1 + r_M \cos \theta_p \dot{\theta}_1 + x_{TMD} \right) \end{aligned}$$

Inertial force in the y-direction (this is only relevant for relatively large θ_p values and can be ignored if the TMDs are centered):

$$T_y = \frac{1}{2}m_{TMD} \left(r_M \cos(\theta_p + \theta_1) + x_{TMD} \tan \theta_1 \right)^2 \quad (\text{A.4})$$

Differentiating with respect to each DOF and neglecting second order terms assuming small angles:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{dT_y}{dx_1} \right) &= 0 \\ \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{dT_y}{d\theta_1} \right) &= \left(-r_M \cos \theta_p \dot{\theta}_1 - r_M \sin \theta_p \right) m_{TMD} \left(-r_M \sin \theta_p \dot{\theta}_1 + x_{TMD} \dot{\theta}_1 \right) = m_{TMD} r_M^2 \sin^2(\theta_p) \dot{\theta}_1 \\ \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{dT_y}{d\theta_2} \right) &= 0 \\ \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{dT_y}{dx_{TMD}} \right) &= \theta_1 m_{TMD} \left(-r_M \sin \theta_p \dot{\theta}_1 + x_{TMD} \dot{\theta}_1 \right) = 0 \end{aligned}$$

The contribution to inertial forces of TMD_i in the platform is given by the following matrix

$$M = M_b + \begin{bmatrix} m_{TMD} & m_{TMD}r_M \cos \theta_p & 0 & \dots & m_{TMD} \\ m_{TMD}r_M \cos \theta_p & m_{TMD}r_M^2 (\cos^2(\theta_p) + \sin^2(\theta_p)) & 0 & \dots & m_{TMD}r_M \cos \theta_p \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ m_{TMD} & m_{TMD}r_M \cos \theta_p & 0 & \dots & m_{TMD} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$V = \frac{1}{2}K_{TMD}x_{TMD}^2 + m_{TMD}g \left(r_M \cos(\theta_p + \theta_1) - x_{TMD} \tan(\theta_t) \right) \quad (A.5)$$

$$\frac{dV}{dx_1} = 0$$

$$\frac{dV}{d\theta_1} = m_{TMD}g \left(r_M (-\cos \theta_p \theta_1 - \sin \theta_p) - x_{TMD} \right)$$

$$\frac{dV}{d\theta_2} = 0$$

$$\frac{dV}{dx_{TMD}} = K_{TMD}x_{TMD} - m_{TMD}g \theta_1$$

Note that $\frac{dV}{d\theta_1}$ contains the constant term $-m_{TMD}gr_M \sin \theta_p$. However if each TMD's mass is evenly distributed amongst the three cylinders, this term cancels off.

The resulting terms added to the stiffness matrix are shown below:

$$K = K_b + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & -m_{TMD}gr_M \cos \theta_p & 0 & \dots & -m_{TMD}g \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & -m_{TMD}g & 0 & \dots & K_{TMD} \end{bmatrix}$$

The damping term only adds a coefficient D_{TMD} to element $(3 + N_i, 3 + N_i)$ of the damping matrix.

In the tower

If the TMD is located in the tower (bigger than 0), the TMD must be placed along the tower central axis for feasibility reasons, therefore no offset angle is present. However, the additional motion of the tower has to be considered:

$$T = \frac{1}{2} m_{TMD} \left(\dot{x}_1 + MC \sin \dot{\theta}_1 + R_{TMD} \sin \dot{\theta}_2 + x_{TMD} \right)^2 \quad (\text{A.6})$$

where MC is the distance from the metacentre to the base of the tower.

Differentiating with respect to each DOF and with respect to time:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{dT}{dx_1} \right) = m_{TMD} \ddot{x}_1 + m_{TMD} MC \ddot{\theta}_1 + m_{TMD} R_{TMD} \ddot{\theta}_2 + m_{TMD} \dot{x}_{TMD} \quad (\text{A.7})$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{dT}{d\dot{\theta}_1} \right) = m_{TMD} MC \dot{x}_1 + m_{TMD} MC^2 \dot{\theta}_1 + m_{TMD} MC R_{TMD} \dot{\theta}_2 + m_{TMD} MC \dot{x}_{TMD} \quad (\text{A.8})$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{dT}{d\dot{\theta}_2} \right) = m_{TMD} R_{TMD} \dot{x}_1 + m_{TMD} R_{TMD} MC \dot{\theta}_1 + m_{TMD} R_{TMD}^2 \dot{\theta}_2 + m_{TMD} R_{TMD} \dot{x}_{TMD} \quad (\text{A.9})$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{dT}{dx_{TMD}} \right) = m_{TMD} \dot{x}_1 + m_{TMD} MC \dot{\theta}_1 + m_{TMD} R_{TMD} \dot{\theta}_2 + m_{TMD} \ddot{x}_4 \quad (\text{A.10})$$

$$(\text{A.11})$$

The contribution to the inertia matrix is shown below:

$$M = M_b + \begin{bmatrix} m_{TMD} & m_{TMD}MC & m_{TMD}R_{TMD} & \dots & m_{TMD} \\ m_{TMD}MC & m_{TMD}MC^2 & m_{TMD}MC R_{TMD} & \dots & m_{TMD}MC \\ m_{TMD}R_{TMD} & m_{TMD}MC R_{TMD} & m_{TMD}R_{TMD}^2 & \dots & m_{TMD}R_{TMD} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ m_{TMD} & m_{TMD}MC & m_{TMD}R_{TMD} & \dots & m_{TMD} \end{bmatrix}$$

For the potential function:

$$V = \frac{1}{2}K_{TMD}x_{TMD}^2 + m_{TMD}g \left(R_{TMD}\cos(\theta_2) + H_c\cos(\theta_1) - x_{TMD}\tan(\theta_2) \right) \quad (A.12)$$

Differentiating with respect to each DOF:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dV}{dx_1} &= 0 \\ \frac{dV}{d\theta_1} &= -m_{TMD}gH_c\theta_1 \\ \frac{dV}{d\theta_2} &= -m_{TMD}gR_{TMD}\theta_2 - m_{TMD}gx_{TMD} \\ \frac{dV}{dx_{TMD}} &= K_{TMD}x_{TMD} - m_{TMD}g\theta_2 \end{aligned}$$

The contribution to the stiffness matrix is:

$$K = K_b + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & -m_{TMD}gH_c & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -m_{TMD}gR_{TMD} & \dots & -m_{TMD}g \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & -m_{TMD}g & \dots & K_{TMD} \end{bmatrix}$$

Appendix B

Derivation of linear damping

The linearised aerodynamic damping derived by Garrad for a fixed-pitch and fixed-speed wind turbine is derived here. Variables refer to Figure 3.13 and are summarised below:

- U : upstream wind velocity
- Ω : Turbine angular velocity
- R and r : turbine radius and position along radius
- a and a' : respectively the axial and tangential induction factors
- ρ : air density (1.25 kg/m^3)
- c : airfoil chord length
- ϕ, θ, α : respectively the inflow angle, blade twist angle and angle of attack
- C_L and C_D : respectively the lift and drag coefficients
- B : number of blade on turbine (in general $B = 3$)

Assuming $U_r = \Omega r(1 + a')$ and $U_d = U(1 - a) \pm x_{top}$, the following assumptions have to be taken:

- small inflow angle ϕ ($\cos\phi \approx 1$)
- high tip speed ratio $\frac{\Omega R}{U}$
- attached flow ($C_l \gg C_d$)

The normal (i.e. thrust) force on a blade section is usually written as:

$$\frac{dF_B}{dr} = \frac{1}{2}\rho W^2 c (C_L \cos\phi + C_D \sin\phi) \quad (\text{B.1})$$

where W is the apparent wind velocity

$$W = \sqrt{(U(1 - a))^2 + (\Omega r(1 + a'))^2} \quad (\text{B.2})$$

From the assumptions taken above this can be simplified to:

$$\frac{dF_B}{dr} = \frac{1}{2}\rho U_r^2 C_L c \quad (\text{B.3})$$

The inflow angle ϕ can also be approximated as $\phi \approx \frac{U_d}{U_r}$.

For a constant speed turbine, $d\phi \approx \frac{dU_d}{U_r}$.

The slope of the lift coefficient is written as $C'_L = \frac{dC_L}{d\alpha}$ where $\alpha = \phi - \beta$. The twist angle β can be assumed constant, therefore:

$$dC_L = C'_L d\phi = C'_L \frac{dU_d}{U_r}. \quad (\text{B.4})$$

Differentiating equation B.3 results in:

$$d\left(\frac{dF_B}{dr}\right) = \frac{1}{2}\rho U_r^2 c dC_L = \frac{1}{2}\rho U_r c C'_L dU_d \quad (\text{B.5})$$

The change in relative velocity dU_d can be expressed as a combination of change in incoming wind speed u and structural motion \dot{x} , so that $dU_d = u - \dot{x}$. The change in thrust $T' = d\left(\frac{dF_B}{dr}\right)$ can then be expressed as:

$$T' = \frac{1}{2}\rho U_r c C'_L (u - \dot{x}) = \frac{dc_a}{dr} (u - \dot{x}) \quad (\text{B.6})$$

Integrating along the blade and for the B blades of the rotor, the damping coefficient c_a can finally be expressed as:

$$c_a = \frac{B\rho\Omega}{2} \int_{R_0}^R C'_L c r dr \quad (\text{B.7})$$

Appendix C

Derivation of fatigue damage in frequency domain

The following derivation is based on the assumptions taken in section 4.1.2 for fatigue damage: the Basquin's relation can be extended into the fatigue limit domain as steel under variable loading will not exhibit a fatigue limit. This makes Palmgren-Miner's rule still relevant.

The derivation steps are based on those given in [44].

The contribution of each stress amplitude to damage is given by:

$$D = \sum_i \frac{n_i}{N(s_i)} \quad (\text{C.1})$$

A first derivation will be made for a narrow-banded input spectrum, which assumes that each peak corresponds to a zero-crossing. In this case, the number of cycles (and therefore peaks) per unit time are given by v_0^+ .

For a Gaussian process, which is usually assumed for wind and wave excitations, this zero-crossing frequency is given by:

$$v_0^+ = \frac{1}{2\pi} \left(\frac{\sigma_{\dot{s}}}{\sigma_s} \right) \quad (\text{C.2})$$

The rms value of s and \dot{s} are obtained from the power spectral density of stress from the following relationships:

$$\sigma_s^2 = \int_0^\infty S_{ss}(\omega) d\omega \quad (\text{C.3})$$

$$\sigma_{\dot{s}}^2 = \int_0^\infty \omega^2 S_{ss}(\omega) d\omega \quad (\text{C.4})$$

$$(\text{C.5})$$

The PSD of stress can be obtained once the PSD of $\theta_2 - \theta_1$ is known from the dynamic model, using the following relationship:

$$s = \frac{(\theta_2 - \theta_1)K_t r_t}{I_t} \quad (\text{C.6})$$

The average damage per unit time \bar{D} can then be obtained from equation C.1:

$$D_{NB}^- = v_0^+ E\left[\frac{1}{N(s)}\right] = v_0^+ \int_0^\infty \frac{p(s)}{N(s)} ds \quad (\text{C.7})$$

The average damage caused per cycle $E\left[\frac{1}{N(s)}\right]$ depends on the probability density distribution of the peaks. For a random process with Gaussian distribution, the probability density function is written as:

$$p(s) = \frac{s}{\sigma_s^2} e^{-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{s}{\sigma_s}\right)^2} \quad (\text{C.8})$$

Next, the Basquin relation for $N(s)$ is used:

$$N(s) = C s^{-k} \quad (\text{C.9})$$

Combining all these equations results in the following expression for the average damage per unit time:

$$D_{NB}^- = \left(\frac{v_0^+ T}{C \sigma_s^2}\right) \int_0^\infty s^{k+1} e^{-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{s}{\sigma_s}\right)^2} ds \quad (\text{C.10})$$

$$D_{NB}^- = \frac{v_0^+}{\alpha} (\sqrt{2\sigma_s})^k \Gamma\left(\frac{k+2}{2}\right) \quad (\text{C.11})$$

where $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is defined as:

$$\Gamma(z) = \int_0^\infty t^{z-1} e^{-t} dt \quad (\text{C.12})$$

Tovo and Benasciutto suggest an empirically derived correction to the narrow-banded result in order to take more realistic broad-banded spectra into account. The correction is taken from [50] and given as follows:

$$D_{TB}^- = [b + (1-b)\alpha_2^{k-1}] \alpha_2 D_{NB}^- \quad (\text{C.13})$$

where

$$\alpha_i = \frac{m_i}{\sqrt{m_0 m_{2i}}} \quad (\text{C.14})$$

$$m_i = \int_0^\infty \omega^i S_{ss}(\omega) d\omega \quad (\text{C.15})$$

$$b = \min\left(\frac{\alpha_1 - \alpha_2}{1 - \alpha_1}, 1\right) \quad (\text{C.16})$$

$$(\text{C.17})$$

